

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT MANAGEMENT

CLAUS, JOE ANTHONY P.

**SURFACING R&D IN THE LEGISLATIVE PROCESS: AN
ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE JOURNAL OF PROCEEDINGS
OF A CITY GOVERNMENT’S COMMITTEE HEARING ON AN AGRICULTURAL
ORDINANCE**

Thesis Adviser:

JEAN A. SALUDADEZ, PhD
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

09 September 2024

Permission of the classification of this academic work access is subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy, and any contractual obligations:

Invention (I)	☐ Yes or ☒ No
Publication (P)	☐ Yes or ☒ No
Confidential (C)	☒ Yes or ☐ No
Free (F)	☒ Yes or ☐ No

Student’s Signature:
Thesis Adviser Signature:

University Permission Page

SURFACING R&D IN THE LEGISLATIVE PROCESS: AN ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE JOURNAL OF PROCEEDINGS OF A CITY GOVERNMENT'S COMMITTEE HEARING ON AN AGRICULTURAL ORDINANCE

"I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page."

"I specifically allow the University to:

Specifically, I grant the following rights to the University:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and in any other databases available on the public internet*
- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing "fair use" of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes.*

Joe Anthony P. Claus | Sept 09, 2024
Signature over Student Name and Date

Acceptance Page:

This thesis titled: **“SURFACING R&D IN THE LEGISLATIVE PROCESS: AN ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE JOURNAL OF PROCEEDINGS OF A CITY GOVERNMENT’S COMMITTEE HEARING ON AN AGRICULTURAL ORDINANCE”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Master of Research and Development Management.

DR. JEAN A. SALUDADEZ
Chair, Thesis Committee

October 22, 2024
(Date)

DR. LEO MENDEL D. ROSARIO
Member, Thesis Committee

October 28, 2024
(Date)

DR. DIGNA D. MANZANILLA
Member, Thesis Committee

October 28, 2024
(Date)

DR. JOANE V. SERRANO
Dean
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

09 September 2024

Biographical Sketch

Joe Anthony P. Claus, called as Sasuke by many, has cultivated a diverse and impactful career, rooted in a passion for the arts and community service. His journey began in 2004 as a member of Tanghalang Dal'wa-Singko, the official College Theater Guild of the University of Batangas, where he later became a trainer in 2020. His college years were marked by achievements in campus journalism, winning several awards at Luzon Area press conferences.

In 2017, Joe graduated with an AB in Political Science from the University of Batangas under the Expanded Tertiary Education Equivalency and Accreditation Program (ETEEAP). His commitment to youth development and education is evident in his role as a Licensed Professional Teacher for Secondary Education-Social Studies and his contributions as a module creator and resource speaker for the Department of Social Welfare and Development Office CALABARZON Region in 2021. Joe's expertise in public relations was recognized with his appointment as a Public Relations and Communications Officer in a political party list organization.

His artistic leadership flourished as he directed community theater productions and served as Technical Director for the Bb. Lungsod ng Batangas Talent and Pageant Nights in 2022 and 2023. A respected figure in his community, Joe is a sought-after judge for cultural competitions in Batangas City and a dedicated event host for the city government's cultural programs. In 2024, he was honored as a scholar of the Development Academy of the Philippines for Futures and Foresight Planning and became an Internal Quality Auditor for ISO 9001:2015 of the Batangas City Government. His commitment to service extends to his involvement with the Rotary Club of Batangas, advising the Rotaract and Interact Clubs, and fostering the next generation of leaders.

As he graduates from the University of the Philippines Open University with a Master of Research and Development Management, Joe Anthony P. Claus stands as a testament to the power of dedication, creativity, and civic engagement.

Acknowledgment

I extend my deepest gratitude to the distinguished faculty and mentors from the University of the Philippines Open University, whose expertise and encouragement have been instrumental in the completion of my Master of Research and Development Management thesis. I am particularly indebted to Dr. Jean A. Saludadez, whose philosophy of learning, relearning, and unlearning anew has profoundly reshaped my approach to research. Her unwavering presence and insightful guidance have been the cornerstone of my academic journey.

I am grateful to Dr. Leo Mendel D. Rosario, the Program Chair for D/MRDM, for his steadfast support and invaluable advice throughout my studies. Similarly, I owe a debt of gratitude to Dr. Digna O. Manzanilla, who, as my Faculty-in-Charge, provided guidance and support in several courses, enriching my educational experience and special thanks are due to Dr. Jane Cadoc-Reyes for her readiness and openness to provide consultations, which greatly benefited my R&DM coursework.

I would like to acknowledge DBA, my eternal supporter, friend, challenger, and cheerleader, along with her family Kuya Kelly, Matt, and Kyle, I am forever grateful for a decade of unwavering belief in my potential. To DJB, for his confidence in my abilities and for inspiring me to strive for greatness. Ms. Chateryn V. Jabon deserves a heartfelt mention as my moral compass and an unwitting mentor, whose patience and guidance have significantly shaped my professional path. As they call her Momshie, ICMA, she was like the mother who birthed the soul of this study, surfacing R&D in enacting agricultural ordinance.

To my Trios – Yntel, Keh, SKs—Mae and Charlene, and Otep, Rox, and Gizelle—thank you for being pillars in my life. My appreciation also goes to my Sangguniang Panlungsod Family, especially Atty. Alyssa Renee A. Cruz and Atty. Olive D. Telegatos, for their generosity, understanding, and the myriad learning opportunities provided.

I must also acknowledge those unnamed but no less significant individuals—my brothers and sisters from various walks of life: FREAKS, our bonds remain unbreakable, transcending time and distance. You know who you are and what you mean to me.

My appreciation extends to my Tanghalang Dal'wa-Singko family: the enrolled, certified, and alumni; who provided a sanctuary for rest and creative expression, enriching my life beyond measure.

Lastly, I am blessed to have the unwavering love and support of my family, Inay[†], TJ, my siblings, and nephews and nieces, who have been my strength and motivation. Above all, I thank God Almighty for the countless blessings and the strength to pursue my academic aspirations.

This thesis stands as a testament to the collective effort and belief of all those mentioned, and it is with sincere appreciation that I acknowledge their contributions.

Dedication

This thesis is a testament to the journey of exploration and discovery that extends beyond the confines of research and academic rigor. It is with profound gratitude and deep respect that I dedicate this work to those who have been the pillars of support and beacons of inspiration throughout this scholarly pursuit.

To my beloved family, whose unwavering faith and love have been my sanctuary and strength. Your sacrifices have not gone unnoticed, and your encouragement has been the wind beneath my wings. To my parents, whose wisdom and guidance have shaped my character and aspirations, this achievement mirrors your enduring commitment to my growth.

To my mentors and professors at the University of the Philippines - Open University, especially those within the Master of Research and Development Management program, for igniting the spark of curiosity and for challenging me to reach new heights. Your dedication to imparting knowledge and fostering critical thinking has left an indelible mark on my academic and professional trajectory.

To my peers and colleagues, for the camaraderie and intellectual exchange that enriched this experience. The shared moments of triumph and tribulation have forged bonds that transcend the pages of this thesis.

To the unseen forces of nature and the higher power that governs the universe, for the serendipitous encounters and fortuitous events that have steered my path towards this moment of accomplishment.

This thesis also honors the spirit of inquiry and the pursuit of knowledge that the University of the Philippines - Open University champions. May the findings and insights gleaned from this research contribute to the tapestry of innovation and development management.

Lastly, to future scholars who will tread this path, may this work serve as a beacon for progressive activism, guiding you towards your own discoveries and successes.

In dedicating this thesis, I am reminded that no endeavor is a solitary feat, and this culmination is a mosaic of the many hands, hearts, and minds that have touched my life. Thank you, from the depths of my heart, for being part of my journey.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	v
Dedication	vii
Table of Contents	ix
Abstract	xi
CHAPTER I: RATIONALE	
R&D and Legislation	1
The Need for R&D-Informed Policy Making	4
CHAPTER II: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	
The Role of Research in Policy Making	6
Enablers and Barriers to Evidence-Based Policy-Making	9
R&D in Agriculture	10
R&D in the Formulation of Ordinances	11
CHAPTER III: RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS	
Research Framework	14
Research Questions	16
CHAPTER IV: METHODOLOGY	
The Ethnomethodological Approach	18
Research Locale	19
Research Participants	20

Research Procedures	21
Data Collection	22
Data Analysis Procedure	23
Presentation of Data	24
Themes, Sub-themes, and Codes Generation	24
CHAPTER V: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	
Role of Forms of Knowledge	47
Certification and Regulation	49
Communication and Education	53
Community and Health	58
Environmental and Economic Impacts	62
Innovative Agricultural Practices	65
Language Patterns and Communication	69
Organic Farming Development	69
Supply Chain and Production Management	73
Financial Planning and Resource Allocation	76
Integration of R&D Formulating Agricultural Ordinances	83
Organizational Dynamics and Support Systems	84
Legislative Processes and Material Distribution	87
Program Execution and Support	91
Legislative Clarity and Framework	93
Organic Farming Legislation and Aspirations	96
Integration Model: R&D in the Legislative Process	100
CHAPTER VI: RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	
Summary	103
Conclusion	106
Recommendations	110
Methodological	110
Practical	112
REFERENCES	114

APPENDICES	116
LIST OF TABLE	
Table 1. Themes, Sub-themes, and Codes Generated	24
Table 2. Type of Knowledge Classification from Generated Codes	48
Table 3. Source of Statement of Generated Codes	83
LIST OF FIGURE	116
Figure 1. Integration of R&D in the Legislative Process of Formulating Agricultural Ordinance	100
TRANSCRIPT	117

Abstract

This study examines the critical role of research and development (R&D) in local legislative policymaking, particularly in the creation of ordinances within local government units (LGUs). It explores how R&D is integrated into the legislative process to improve governance and agricultural policies. The research aims to understand the methods used by legislative departments to develop ordinances and the impact of R&D on policy legislation. The findings may reveal gaps in current policies and offer a framework for incorporating R&D into evidence-based policy formulation, leading to better-informed and sustainable agricultural practices.

The study used ethnomethodology to analyze the legislative department's committee hearings, focusing on the social organization of interactions. This research will involve detailed data analysis to decode local governance operations, aiming to provide a comprehensive account of legislative procedures and contribute to ordinance development and understanding social interactions.

The thesis examines the crucial, yet often informal role of Research and Development (R&D) in city government legislation, particularly in agricultural policy-making. It reveals that council members' knowledge and language use reflect R&D's influence, despite the lack of formal R&D structures. The study suggests that integrating R&D more systematically into the legislative process could improve policy efficacy and benefit the community.

Keywords: Legislative Policymaking; Research and Development; Agricultural Policies; Ethnomethodology; and Evidence-Based Legislation

Chapter I

RATIONALE

Research and Development (R&D) is opined to provide a foundation not just for an informed decision-making but also for an effective policy formulation, a pivotal role in legislative processes. As a crucial framework of the legislative process, it is a potent solution government seeks to address societal challenges. With the use of an ethnomethodological approach, the integration of R&D insights, as explored in this thesis, presents and discusses the imperative role of R&D as observed in the forms of knowledge, and language patterns and communication manifested by the stakeholders involved in the local level policy making. It aims to identify the presence of significant relationship that exists in the helices of R&D, legislative mandate, and public policy formulation.

R&D and Legislation

R&D is often associated with the common notion as an offshoot of technology creation and innovation, but its importance transcends beyond technological advancements. In the discipline of local governance, R&D can either be observed implicitly or explicitly, nevertheless, it is a crucial support system in the legislative mandate of public policy formulation. The nature of public policy formulation as a process is indeed complex. It requires technical understanding of the systems and subsystems that contributes and affects the effective enactment of public policies. As the significant role and presence of R&D remains unrecognized in the context of local legislation of

policy in form of ordinances, this paper aims to identify and bridge the gap that exists by locating the presence of R&D in a city level process of formulating policies, embedded in a documented information classified as the Journal of Proceeding of Committee Hearing conducted in a city government's legislative department.

The ambiguousness of R&D role, the need for an imperative inclusion or integration of R&D findings in local ordinances formulation, and the challenges posted in harmonizing the expertise of stakeholders in the dissected field of policy making and scientific domain are aimed to be bridged by this thesis by highlighting the necessity for an enhanced capacity of local legislators and relevant stakeholders in a collaborated approach of evidence-based policy making. Shortening this gap is inversely related to the lengthening the probability of coming up with an effective, informed, sustainable, responsive, and innovative public policy. Thus, employing an ethnomethodological approach in this study frames the realization of enhancing and utilizing the legislative R&D in the realm of public governance.

Legislative R&D as an unrecognized research aspect. The research arm of R&D is often overlooked in legislation. On a general knowledge, R&D is perceived as an output of technological underpinnings and scientific breakthroughs, but its vital role is not formally recognized as framework in the legislative department of a city government. Though local legislative bodies engage in performing research, as the research arm of 'research' and 'development', R&D is an overlooked aspect and a process regarded and limited to simple research arm of legislative R&D that is limited to gathering of facts and consultation to stakeholders. Thus, creating a significant gap in recognizing the vitality of research in legislative functions.

Clarity and specificity of R&D framework in policy formulation. Rigorous research and data analysis are vital components of the drafting process of local policies as these

components are precursors in identifying emerging trends, signal factors, and best practices that can be adopted and can affect the formulation of public policies. This is a prime reason why R&D needs to be identified as solid framework included and observe in the performance of legislative mandate and performance of public policy formulation.

Balancing local context with generalizable findings. What can also be opined as the challenge is how to balance the local context with the generalizable findings from R&D studies. The local context at the city level may differ significantly from the national or regional context, which can affect the relevance and applicability of R&D findings. Local policymakers must navigate the expanse field policy inputs and basis surfing in the tides of localized context of ordinances and the generalized national goals it must address.

Limited capacity for evidence-based policymaking. As how the maxim 'leaders are not managers and managers are not leaders' differentiates leadership and management, local legislators are not all the time experienced researchers, vis-à-vis, R&D practitioners or research managers are not always local legislators. Thus, it is somehow uncommon for a local policy maker to have high capacity to evaluate and include R&D outputs as evidences or bases for formulating local ordinances. If this limited capabilities will be converted into a strong suite of a policy initiator, R&D then will be a staple input of policy making in terms of how to enhance the capacity of local policymakers to evaluate R&D outputs and translate them into evidence-based policies critically.

Lack of institutional mechanism. In the specified study area, R&D in the form of Research and Development Division or Research and Community Extension Unit exist but not in the legislative department. The absence of a dedicated and operational Research and Development (R&D) division unfolds a significant gap in institutional structure. This lack of a formalized R&D section plainly exposes the reality that when

there is no established mechanism to systematically manage the research components, policy formulation process is hollowed on the basic evidenced-based and necessary informed policy-making. Though the responsibility of conducting research falls on co-terminus and job order employees, still a permanent and specialized R&D unit is missing and the formulation process may lack the consistency and depth that a structured research department would provide.

The Need for R&D-informed Policy Making

The role uniquely played by R&D in changing phase of local governance has become evidently pivotal. Local governance now grapples As local governance now grapple with complex challenges, fronting the legislative department with task of formulating policies that are effective, responsive to, and inclusive for the needs of the public. Crafting agricultural ordinances for integrated component city, like for the locale of the study, as local government mandates are essential in directing and propelling agriculture's advancement and sustainability. It is the duty of the City Council, serving as the city's legislative arm, to craft these regulations. Comprehending the significance of R&D in crafting these policies can shed light on the formulation of policies grounded in empirical evidence. Yet, there is a noticeably limited understanding of how R&D influences the formulation of agricultural ordinances within the City's legislative department.

Exploring and integrating R&D findings in legislation. Exploring and integrating R&D findings into the legislative process is a critical, yet beneficial challenge for a city government that aims to enhance its policy development. While R&D is a cornerstone in crafting local ordinances, compressing the divide between research outcomes and their

application in policy making remains a challenge. To overcome this, the necessity of implementing strategies and methods based on a R&D-embracing legislative framework must be constructed and institutionalized to seamlessly blend R&D insights into policy deliberations, as this ensures that empirical evidence drives legislative propositions. Establishing this synergistic relationship bears essence to effective governance, as it enables local legislators to come up with decisions rooted in solid research, leading to more successful policy outcomes. By including R&D into the curriculum of legislative processes, lawmakers are capacitated more to tackle the various issues affronting the society, leading to an ultimate fostering of a more informed and proactive approach to local legislation.

Capacity of local government to establish Legislative R&D Division. The creation of plantilla positions and allocating annual budget to sustain the operation of this division is a serious matter that must pass the feasibility and capacity of a local government to support its operation. There might be no problem in the employing of qualified R&D managers and workers, but the lifetime operation of this division needs careful, strategic, and sustainable planning, and continuous capacity building.

Considering all the gaps and issues presented, this thesis stands to provide evidence-based information and research-based findings in the exploration of surfacing R&D in the legislative process under the lens of an ethnomethodological analysis of the Journal of Proceedings of a city government's committee hearing on an agricultural ordinance.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter presents the curated and reviewed related literature focused in the pivotal role research played in the shaping policies, the dynamics of evidence-based policymaking, including its enablers and barriers, and the significant impact of research and development (R&D) in agriculture and ordinance formulation. Through a systematic exploration of these topics, the chapter aims to surface the complementing relationship between theoretical research and practical policy applications, underscoring the importance of informed decision-making in the local government legislative process.

The Role of Research in Policy Making

The concept of making decisions based on solid evidence, a standard in the developed world, is increasingly being embraced by lower and middle-income nations. Several theories have been proposed to explain the role of research evidence in policy making.

The study of Tariq and Zakir (2003) stated that though there is a growing global trend toward leveraging scientific research evidence in developing public health policies, it was highlighted that policymakers also consider various other forms of information, aside from R&D findings. This research was also focused in exploring the policymakers' views on 'evidence' and its collection and utilization in policy development and execution. With qualitative methods utilized in the study, empirical data from document analysis and semi-structured survey and in-depth interviews were gathered from 87 selected policymakers between December 2022 and October 2023. Grounded theory principles

was used in the data analysis. Data structuring was done by using a conceptual model for Evidence-Informed Policy Formulation and Implementation as influenced by Bowen and Zwi frameworks and Dodson et al.'s work. Key themes that were identified by in the research are, as follows: Evidence Quality, Relevance, Viability, Timeliness; Researcher Expertise, and Limitations of leadership/Political Influence on organizational Culture and Workflow.

In 2015, Onwujekwe, et. al., (2015) presented that policy development was systematic in terms of integrating pertinent evidence at every stage. Policymakers treated and utilized 'evidence' broadly, and not just as plain research findings. The application and integration of evidence in policy decisions and execution is regarded to be complex. The complexity is dictated by the participants' local nuances, policymakers' perceptions, and organizational dynamics. Moreover, the intricacies depicted in health policy formulation are increasingly recognized, particularly in the context of low- and middle-income nations where evidence utilization is an emerging field. Cognitive and institutional dynamics significantly influence the application of evidence within policy frameworks. This study focuses in the utilization of various evidence forms in shaping health policies in Nigeria. Three distinct policy scenarios were generated from the employment of evidence that underwent comparative analysis: (1) integrated maternal neonatal and child health strategy (IMNCH); (2) oral health (OH) policy; and (3) human resource for health (HRH) policy. The research methodology involved thorough and systematic document analysis evidenced by its 31 comprehensive interviews conducted with pivotal policy stakeholders, with the Framework Approach facilitating data examination, supported by NVivo 10 software.

The common knowledge was formed: 'that evidence should be tangible and factual to bolster decision-making.' Contextual relevance, accessibility, and timeliness were

identified as key factors enhancing the utilization of evidence. The Lancet series were tagged as an inexpensive yet impactful resource in then formulation of the IMNCH policy. Accordingly, HRH and OH policies incorporated both formal and informal evidence, whereas the IMNCH's formulation predominantly relied on formal evidence. Generally, formal evidence like survey findings and scholarly articles were deemed most beneficial during the agenda-setting phase to pinpoint policy necessities, thereby kick-starting the policy-creation process. Both international and domestic evidence played a role in substantiating policy needs and crafting policies, albeit to a lesser extent in devising implementation strategies. In conclusion, acknowledging the significance of diverse evidence types and establishing mechanisms for their generation and application can significantly advance evidence-informed health policy development in Nigeria and comparable settings.

Another reviewed literature stated that improving the proper use of research evidence is a common wisdom. Oxman, et al. (2009), further stated that despite of this common wisdom empirical evidence to support such claim is difficult. The researcher's conduct of systematic reviews of studies prove that (1) the likelihood of research being used by policymakers is increased by the interaction between researchers and policymakers; (2) the inverse relationship of good timing and poor timing pulls and pushes the chance of research utilization by policymakers; (3) the likelihood of research being used by policymakers decreases because policymakers have negative attitudes towards research evidence; (4) the likelihood of research being used by policymakers decreases when policymakers lack relevant R&D skills and expertise; (5) the likelihood of research being used by policymakers increases when policy networks and trust in researchers are present; (6) factors such as lack of perceived relevance, the use of jargon, and the

production of publications aimed at a scholarly audience are decrease the likelihood of research being used by policymakers.

Enablers and Barriers to Evidence-based Policy Making

UK National Health Service (NHS) was the locale of the study conducted by Elliott and Popay (2000) that presented a qualitative study that on the exploration of the enablers and barriers of evidence-based policy-making at a local level. According to the study, the direct impact of research evidence in decision-making was moderated by several factors: financial constraints, changing deadlines, and decision-makers' experiential knowledge. In indirect ways, research was more likely to influence policy in terms of informing policy debate and facilitating communication between service providers and users. The study concluded with an emphasis on the importance of ongoing dialogue between researchers and the users of research in enhancing the uptake of research-based evidence in the policy process.

The study of Ellen (2018) et al., complements the other studies previously cited. The international similarity rises in the acknowledgement complexity of health policy decision-making and the recognition of the challenge of bridging the gap between research, practice, and policy. Though different contexts and actors may have different perspectives on how decisions are made and what evidence is used, still, a similarity exists as some explored factors that hinder the use of evidence in policy was noted such as political and economic constraints that are beyond the control of health policy researchers and policymakers.

In addition, the studies of Mitton, et al. (2007), Campbell, et al. (2009) and Orton, et al. (2011) published that relevance, packaging, and accessibility of research are areas where researchers and policymakers can influence the integration of evidence in bridging

policy gaps. According to their studies, there is a need for policymakers to be open to evidence-informed policy-making. This requires them to have the knowledge and skills to access and apply research evidence in policy formulation. Lacking the effective mechanisms in obtaining research findings and evidences in times of need lowers the chance of coming up with research and evidence-based policy.

R&D in Agriculture

Agricultural R&D advances and sustains agricultural practices and policies, like a cornerstone of an edifice. Anandajayasekeram (2011) conducted a study entitled "The Role of Agricultural R&D within the Agricultural Innovation Systems Framework". This study narrated the evolution of agricultural innovation systems and their significance for R&D. The study highlights the agricultural transition from traditional to modern practices and emphasizes the importance of generating, accessing, and utilizing knowledge as components of the innovation as a process. With the study's framework, the dynamic interactions among various stakeholders and the critical role of institutions in shaping innovation outcomes were acknowledged. The necessity of learning and adapting to local contexts to facilitate remarkable and sustainable innovation processes was also underscored.

Recently in 2022, Estoian, et al. published that R&D investments are pivotal to farmers' realization of income, which extends to attainment of sustainable development. The researchers emphasized the positive correlation between governmental agricultural R&D expenditure and economic prosperity across most EU member states. It confirms that a "significant portion of farmers' income growth can be attributed to these expenditures, which may influence macroeconomic policy and the direction of agricultural

R&D spending, particularly in rural areas aiming to achieve sustainable development goals.”

The study by Kristiansen, Taji, and Reganold titled "Organic Agriculture: A Global Perspective" (2020) enlightened the discipline of R&D as they pronounced that R&D evidences drive the global shift towards organic farming practices. Accordingly, the socioeconomic benefits of organic agriculture are improved soil health, biodiversity conservation, and enhanced farmer livelihoods, and the mentioned benefits are affronted with while the challenges of widespread adoption.

These studies can be collectively summarized as literatures that underscore the transformative power of R&D in agriculture. It was revealed how strategic investments and policy reforms can lead to innovation, economic growth, and sustainable development. With the presented literatures, the interconnectedness of R&D expenditure, innovation frameworks, and institutional reforms, were demonstrated as factor that highlights their collective impact on the agricultural sector's evolution and the livelihoods of farmers. As the global agricultural landscape continues to change, these studies provide valuable guidance for policymakers and stakeholders in shaping R&D initiatives and policies of the futures of local legislation and public policy formulation.

R&D in the Formulation of Ordinances

To highlight the significance of R&D in shaping agricultural policy and the transition towards organic farming under the application of ethnomethodological analysis in social research, several literatures became bases as backbone of this paper. The study of Gutierrez, et al. (2023) entitled “Agricultural innovation system: Analysis from the subsystems of R&D,” confirmed that training, extension, and sustainability play a pivotal role of R&D in agricultural policy-making exists. It underscores how R&D acts as an

enabler of innovation, shaper of policy decisions and outcomes that ultimately influences the agricultural sector's growth and sustainability.

The exploration of agricultural policy-making is enriched by a diverse array of studies that contribute to the theoretical framework of this field. For instance, Daugbjerg and Swinbank work in "Policy and Society" in 2012, delves into the 'new' politics of agriculture and food, highlighting the broadened agricultural policy agenda that now intersects with domains like food safety, energy supplies, and environmental protection. The cited research discussed how value creates conflicts within the interlinked policy and how issues were managed differently across institutions, thereby influencing policy coordination and conflict resolution. This study underscored the evolution of agricultural policy-making from a segmented approach. It further presented a more integrated approach that shifts traditional agrarian fundamentalism to a multifaceted recognition of agricultural role.

The systematic literature review conducted by Pierrette, Du, and Diakit (2021) was focused on the barriers involved in implementing environmentally sustainable agricultural practices adoption. Their research is grounded in 14 different theories and models, including those from social and behavioral sciences as well as systems-based models developed specifically for sustainable agriculture. The findings from this review suggest that theory-informed research can significantly influence policy and practice, particularly in understanding and overcoming the constraints to adopting sustainable practices. The research published that theory-informed research is pre-conditional to understand and overcome the constraints of adopting sustainable practices.

Pal (2008) provided a comprehensive analysis of the paradigm shifts observed in agricultural-focused research and policy. Accordingly, the paradigm shift observed is said to be primarily driven by scarcity of funds. Citing India and China, as locales of the study,

robust agricultural research systems are precursor to reform initiation leading to diversification of funding resources and increasing of research efficiency. Specifically competitive funding, commercialization of technologies, strengthened intellectual property rights, and flexible extension approaches were source of insights of reform and lesson relevant to other developing countries facing similar challenges.

From the cited literatures, it can be synthesized that nuanced understanding of the connections of scientific research, policy formulation, and social analysis. Evidence-based decision-making in agriculture is very essential in recognizing the value of methodological approaches in understanding the social context of agriculture. Findings from these studies surfaced the current practices which are influential to the conduct of future research directions in the respective field of agriculture, society, and policy making.

Chapter III

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This chapter discusses the research framework adopted in the study. Qualitative approach was chosen to be employed in this study with the use of Ethnomethodology as this is the best lens that can be laid in identifying plausible meanings and contexts as observed from the knowledge, methods, practices, and daily actions related to the performance of duties of local legislators and involved stakeholders, in terms of conduct of committee hearing for the formulation of an agricultural ordinance in a city government.

Research Framework

Ethnomethodology is used in the study both as a framework and a methodology to reveal the interaction between R&D and legislative processes in the creation of agricultural ordinances.

Garfinkel's seminal work, "Ethnomethodology's Role in Social Science Research" (1967), provides a foundational perspective on the use of ethnomethodology to understand and study social phenomena. The ethnomethodological approach, founded by Harold Garfinkel offered a unique perspective in exploring the integration of R&D and its role in the formulation of local agricultural ordinances. Pinning the focus on the everyday practices and interactions of individuals and stakeholders within the Legislative Department of a City Government, ethnomethodology can unearth plausible contexts derived from the adherence to standard rules and procedures in the conduct of committee

hearings and plausible meanings as observed and noted from process of creating and implementing agricultural policies. This approach highlighted the practical reasoning and actions of policymakers as it reveal the level of integration of R&D in local policy formulation. Ethnomethodology's emphasis on members' methods — how people make sense of their world — can elucidate the often unarticulated processes that shape policy decisions, offering a rich qualitative insight into the legislative dynamics of the City Government.

Ethnomethodology, as conceived by Harold Garfinkel, is defined as a framework that scrutinizes the daily methods people employ in living with social realities. It shifts from the traditional to sociological approaches by not presupposing any set of norms or behaviors, rather, by observing the actual practices individuals are engage with in order to maintain social order. This approach is particularly relevant to the researcher as it allows for an in-depth examination of the interaction of local policymakers in the process of integrating R&D into agricultural legislation.

Establishing the relationship of the ethnomethodology evident to the Legislative Department of a City Government, with formulating a local agricultural policy, it can be opined that knowledge and implicit rules within this legislative body inform the creation and enforcement of ordinances. By analyzing the members' methods, or the ways in which the council members make sense of their duties and the information presented to them and the sharing of knowledge and expertise by the stakeholders involved in the committee hearing, one can gain insights into the legislative process that are not immediately apparent through traditional research methods. In example, the manner how local legislators together with the invited resource persons conduct committee hearing involving discussions, debates, and raising of amendments on proposed ordinances is a process that reflects values and priorities evident in public policy formulation.

Ethnomethodology as a qualitative approach of exploring the research topic facilitates the interpretation of inherent forms of knowledge and language patterns and communication as observed from both the legislative department of a city government and the invited resource persons during the conduct of committee hearings for the purpose of formulating local policies. Informal negotiations are uncovered as it provides contextual understanding on the integration of scientific knowledge in the formulation of a local ordinance. This is very crucial not just in the context of agricultural ordinance enactment but on the totality of local ordinances, regardless of the sector issue it addresses. The harmonization of the local culture or organizational culture, the application of forms of knowledge, and the language patterns and communications as reflected by the legislative department and the stakeholders facilitates the creation of effective and sustainable manner of formulating local policies.

It is summarized that ethnomethodology establishes the connection of local legislative practices and integration of R&D. It provides a guided manner to document and analyze the lived experience of policymaking, highlighting the importance of social interactions in shaping agricultural ordinances. This approach complements with the objectives of the graduate thesis of adding depth and clarity to the understanding of legislative processes within the legislative department of a city government.

Research Questions

The main research question that the study attempted to answer is:

How did R&D surface in the process of formulating agricultural ordinances in a city government?

To broaden the discourse and presentation of plausible contexts of the study, the researcher aimed to answer the following specific questions:

1. What role does knowledge play in shaping agricultural ordinances, even when R&D is not explicitly mentioned?
2. How do language patterns and communication within the legislative department of a city government reflect R&D-related discussions?

The study explores on how Research and Development (R&D) in legislative processes surfaces. It investigates how R&D is integrated into the creation of agricultural ordinances, the influence of unspoken knowledge in ordinance shaping, and the reflection of R&D in the language and communication patterns of the legislative department of a city government. The study delves into the current integration of R&D, revealing its subtle yet significant presence even when not directly cited. It also examines the impact of knowledge, which guides ordinance development beyond documented research. Lastly, the study provides an analysis on how the legislative department of a city government uses its unique language patterns and communication in the referenced process and presence of R&D concepts in formulating local policies.

Chapter IV

METHODOLOGY

The thesis adopted ethnomethodology as approach to explore, observe, and analyse the incorporation of R&D in the process of local ordinance formulation in the legislative department of a city government, as based from the documented information called Journal of Proceedings of a Conducted Committee Hearing. It repeatedly dissects the documented information, offering a detailed analysis of the formulation of an ordinance initiated by local legislators and participated by relevant stakeholders, purposively to identify codes, generate sub-themes, and sum up themes as observed from the forms of knowledge, and language patterns and communications.

The Ethnomethodological Approach

Ethnomethodological approach is applied for the purpose of studying how the stakeholders involved: local legislators, smallholder farmers, city agriculturist, and other relevant agricultural organizations perceive R&D and its integration in the formulation of agricultural policies. The social dynamics and interactions and local realities observed from the documented information provided vivid description and accounts vital for the gaining of understanding of the locale's social practices and specific contexts of public policy formulation. Through an ethnomethodological approach, content analysis was employed to probe and discover the lived experiences and sense-making processes observed in the social process of local legislation.

The local of the study, a legislative department of a city government, has long been enacting ordinances and approving resolutions related to the sector of agriculture, as

these are the mandates of its functions and roles. R&D, as backed up by numerous studies, has been performing vital role in shaping agricultural policies and contributing to the field of knowledge management and generation, technology commercialization and transfer, and innovative and sustainable agricultural practices. Under the lens of this approach, the local legislative mandate of the local of the study, the presence and integration of R&D concepts as manifested by the forms of knowledge and language patterns and communication directly observed from the stakeholders: resource persons and local legislators; and the process of public policy formulation were treated as elements that when interplay or interconnect displays a dynamic relationship that facilitates informed decision-making based from empirical evidences and community perspectives.

As ethnomethodological approach extends to gaining of understanding on the role played by R&D in the formulation of local policy in a city government, it paves way on the discovery how R&D-related data, evidences, and findings are integrated in the process of policy formulation. This supports the interplay between local knowledge, policy process, and R&D integration.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the workplace of the researcher, the legislative department of a city government. The city is classified as a prime agro-industrial hub of its region. The legislative department was adjudged as national winner and national finalist in the Local Legislative Award program of the Department of the Interior and Local Government and Philippines' Councilors League in 2018 and 2023, respectively. In 2024, several agricultural ordinances were enacted and the city's first agro-fisheries code is in the process of drafting. As the city provides testament to its commitment in further

advancing its agricultural sector as backed up by implemented ordinances, the researcher decided to select this locale to be the center of the study.

Research Participants

The research participants were drawn from the personalities who were present during the conduct of the committee hearing for the formulation and deliberation of the locale's Organic Agriculture Ordinance. The committee hearing was facilitated by the legislative department through its Agriculture and Cooperatives Committee Chairperson and Members. The committee hearing was attended by other local legislators, the city budget officer, the city agriculturist, and several representatives from smallholder farmers and farming-related organizations.

The local legislators and other attendees were assigned with coded names as follows:

- Chair (the Chairperson of the Committee)
- Member 1 (Local Legislator 1; committee member)
- Member 2 (Local Legislator 2; committee member)
- Member 3 (Local Legislator 3; committee member)
- Member 4 (Local Legislator 4; committee member)
- Resource Person 1 (President: vegetable growers association)
- Resource Person 2 (President: organic farming association)
- Resource Person 3 (Vice President: cacao growers association)
- Resource Person 4 (Member: banana growers association)
- CA (City Agriculturist)
- CBO (City Budget Officer)

The research participants not only enriched the research data but also underscored the importance of multi-stakeholder engagement in the legislative process, particularly when it pertains to sectors as vital as agriculture. An informed consent was received from the Committee Chairperson, so as with the Stenographer who transcribed the documented information, and the Records Officer who archived the documented information.

Research Procedures

The research procedures involved a systematic examination of documented information: the Journal of Proceedings of Conducted Committee Hearing. Research Procedures include data collection and data analysis.

The document had been read multiple times to ensure a thorough understanding of the content and to extract meaningful information about the conducted committee hearing. From the documented information, the researcher had gathered data types relevant to legislative intents, meaningful debates, discussions, and deliberations, and significant decisions and outcomes. The data collection process was instrumental in gathering rich contextual data as it provided detailed understanding of the legislative process in the perspective of the researcher. The non-intrusive process, as this does not require any direct interaction with the participants, also offered historical insight on local legislative changes and current trends.

Indexicality, reflexivity, and accountability were points that were utilized in the process of data analysis. The research examined how the plausibility of actions and direct statements were used and how can these be treated as context-dependent in order to generate contextual cues and clues that makes sense from the displayed interactions. Reflexivity was included in the study by providing a process that analyses the participants'

actions and statements and how these reflect and shape the social order engaged by the participants in formulating local ordinances. The participants' justification and explanations during the committee hearing were investigated and further analysed to determine accountability.

Data Collection

The Journal of Proceedings of the conducted committee hearing for the discussion and formulation of an agricultural ordinance in the legislative department of a city government was the primary source of collected data for the study. The data collection process in this study was primarily structured around the Journal of Proceedings, which provided a comprehensive record of the committee hearings. The iterative nature of the data collection permitted ongoing refinement of the research focus, with each review of the document deepening the understanding of the text and enabling the extraction of significant patterns, codes, and themes that were crucial in addressing the research questions.

In the initial phase of data collection, the researcher engaged in a comprehensive review of the documented proceedings, which entailed a series of iterative readings to identify preliminary patterns and codes. This process aligns with the principles of qualitative data coding, which involves the creation and assignment of labels to categorize data extracts, subsequently used to derive themes and patterns for analysis. The coding was conducted inductively; the data itself informed the development of codes without preconceived categories, thus allowing for the emergence of themes directly from the data.

Data Analysis Procedure

With the iterative and thorough process of reading and note-taking in order to gain strong familiarization with the documented information being analysed, the researcher was able to conduct the coding process. Coding was regarded by the researcher as a word or short phrase that symbolically assigns a summation, salient, and essence capturing of evocative attributes based on recorded transcript. Codes are primary content derived not from a precise science but on interpretative act that is treated by the researcher as a heuristic process. For this study, manual coding was adopted since a single material was analysed along with open coding, axial coding, and selective coding.

The researcher started with open coding or the coding process of labelling the various sections of the documented information that bears significance and relevance to the integration of R&D in the formulation of local agricultural ordinance. As initial codes were grouped into unique categories based on its relationships and commonalities, axial coding was employed. Selective coding was applied after the process of identifying the core themes that could possibly be generated from the categories.

The subsequent stage involved the crucial aspect of qualitative analysis referred to as the generation of sub-themes. The researcher systematically grouped related codes into potential sub-themes that represented underlying patterns in the data. The six-step process developed by Braun and Clarke: familiarization, coding, generation of themes, reviewing of themes, defining and naming and themes, and writing up; founded the analysis of theme.

Theme identification was the final analytical step, where the researcher interpreted the identified sub-themes to discern meaningful central themes that could inform the proposed ordinance's development. Patterns and connections between codes were identified by the researcher as themes display commonality in issues being discussed in

the documented information. Finally, names were assigned to represent the unique themes generated from the data collection process as these themes reflects the underlying and explored concept of integrating R&D in the legislative process of policy formulation.

Presentation of Data

Through meticulous coding and thematic analysis, several key themes emerged from the discussions. These include the (1) role of forms knowledge in shaping agricultural ordinances; (2) language patterns and communication derived from the Journal of Proceedings manuscript reflecting R&D-related discussions; and (3) integration of R&D into the process of formulating agricultural ordinances. Each theme reflects the complex interplay between R&D and policy formulation, shedding light on how empirical data and local knowledge converge in the legislative process. Role of forms of knowledge in shaping agricultural ordinances.

Themes, Sub-themes, and Codes Generated

From the documented information or the Journal of Proceedings of the Committee Hearing conducted about the proposed organic agriculture ordinance, several themes and sub-themes were identified as generated from numerous codes, as follows:

Table 1

Themes, Sub-themes, and Codes Generated

Excerpt	Codes	Sub-themes	Themes
<i>SP Member 2: xxx The use of fertilizers, which contain chemical compositions,</i>	1. usage limits and safety concern	1. Certification and Regulation	1. Role of Forms of Knowledge

<p><i>cannot be said to be safe, although there are certain limits on how to use them. xxx</i></p>			
<p><i>SP Member 2: xxx At OCVAS, all the seeds we distribute, are you certain that those are organic?</i></p>	<p>2. organic certification uncertainty</p>		
<p>City Agriculturist: The budget is already integrated into our ... xxx</p>	<p>3. budget considerations for organic certification</p>		
<p>City Agriculturist: It is necessary because for them to be called organic products or organically grown vegetables and fruits, there must be certifying bodies that will certify that they are organically grown.</p>	<p>4. importance of certification for organic products</p>		
<p>City Agriculturist: What I hear is that certification alone costs sixty thousand (60,000) for a single product, plus there are other fees because many studies need to be conducted.</p>	<p>5. certification cost</p>		
<p>City Agriculturist: It takes several years before you can be granted certification because implementing organic farming takes five (5) years before you can be</p>	<p>6. timeframe for organic certification</p>		

certified as organic practitioners.			
City Agriculturist: What I hear is that certification alone costs sixty thousand (60,000) for a single product, plus there are other fees because many studies need to be conducted. It takes several years before you can be granted certification because implementing organic farming takes five (5) years before you can be certified as organic practitioners.	7. requirements for organic certification		
City Agriculturist: xxx However, the seeds they use are not endemic, they are not hybrid, xxx but that's an assumption because they are not yet certified. xxx but we cannot say they are organic because there are no certifying bodies to certify them.	8. challenges in certification and seed origin		
SP Member 2: xxx it won't proceed unless you have communication with our good City Budget Officer and discuss it thoroughly. xxx	1. interdepartmental communication	2. Communication and Education	
SP Chairperson: Thank you, Mr. Zalada, what we have heard is very educational for us,	2. information dissemination		

we have only heard about it now, xxx			
<p>SP Member 1: Madam SP Chairperson. Let's promote our Organic Farming in schools.</p> <p>SP Member 2: xxx So, maybe as soon as possible we should educate them, teach them the correct process so we can get started. Because if we wait for the right time, I might not get to taste organic food anymore. But we should start as soon as possible to realize and implement this, thank you.</p>	3. educational integration of organic farming		
SP Member 1: xxx. So, I just want to ask what is being watered on the plants.	4. observation of agricultural practices		
SP Member 1: That's what is being watered?	5. verification of organic farming methods		
SP Member 1: The Lakatan bananas are very delicious, xxx and that is what I consider truly organic, madam SP Chairperson.	1. community practices and perceptions of organic produce	3. Community and Health	
City Budget Officer: xxx The problem will be with the buyers; the product is there, it may not be certified but we believe some things	2. consumer preference and market progress		

<p>are organic because they are obtained organically. However, as long as consumers do not appreciate the value of organic produce, our products will not progress because we still prefer to buy even if the Melon has a slight blemish, although it's not deep, it's just on the surface, but we still won't buy it, we will still choose the perfectly smooth melon. The same goes for bananas, eggplants, okra. What's important is, for example, if the okra is much curved, it might be organic but no one will buy such curved okra.</p>			
<p>City Agriculturist: xxx The truth is, our office advocates for the implementation of organic farming here in the City of Batangas. xxx</p>	<p>3. environmental advocacy</p>		
<p>City Agriculturist: xxx can produce healthy and nutritious fruits and vegetables, thus greatly benefiting human health, xxx</p>	<p>4. community health</p>		
<p>Resource Person 2: xxx but now we have so many organic farmers</p>	<p>5. current state of organic farming</p>		

<p>who actually do not know that they are organic farmers. xxx</p>			
<p>City Agriculturist: xxx So, what we will use are natural resources, organic fertilizers from plant and animal waste, which pose minimal risk to the environment, xxx avoiding the destruction of natural habitats or natural resources. The use of chemicals causes the destruction of the ecology or biodiversity of our environment. xxx</p>	<p>1. environmental impact</p>		
<p>City Agriculturist: Therefore, this ordinance will be a great help if implemented here in our City of Batangas, it will also help farmers to be safe from the harmful effects of chemicals and then provide additional income for the farmers.</p>	<p>2. economic impact</p>	<p>4. Environmental and Economic Impacts</p>	
<p>SP Member 1: xxx but do we have identified locations and a mechanism to protect the said farming test?</p>	<p>3. implementation of organic farming test and protection mechanisms for farming tests</p>		
<p>City Agriculturist: Currently, sir, since 2000 we have implemented farming, but we</p>	<p>4. current agricultural practices</p>		

<p>cannot say it is totally organically grown because they use hybrid seeds and organic fertilizers, including organic foliar fertilizer.</p>			
<p>City Budget Officer: xxx there is another way like in the fields when the first harvest of corn is aged and then placed behind the granary to be sun-dried, which is what is used for planting, xxx</p> <p>City Budget Officer: xxx since I grew up on our island where those seeds were really hung behind the granary, and every rainy season, that is what will be sorted by the mothers and then planted again in the fields. xxx</p>	<p>1. traditional knowledge</p>	<p>5. Innovative Agricultural Practices</p>	
<p>Resource Person 1: xxx This wood is burned in a chamber, and the resulting liquid is the wood vinegar. I am already using these methods.</p>	<p>2. application of wood vinegar</p>		
<p>Resource Person 1: In the composting facility, that's what I use for quick decomposition when I water it on my accumulated grass or remaining</p>	<p>3. organic waste management</p>		

waste in the field, the wood vinegar decomposes quickly, xxx			
Resource Person 1: So, what I did before with a drum of water, that's the foliar that serves as a bloom booster fertilizer for the plants.	4. local agricultural practices		
Resource Person 1: So now, in my planting of plants, vegetables, I am also using organic methods. xxx	5. organic farming adoption		
SP Member 1: xxx Do you know of any locations where we can conduct an organic farming test?	6. organic farming test sites		
City Agriculturist: What we have at OCVAS farming is organically grown, we just don't claim it unless certified.	7. organic farming certification and practices		
Resource Person 3: xxx Ma'am, regarding the tissue culture like the one at UP, it is available, but it seems not yet here... We have sometimes acquired it from UP. Tissue culture is done in a laboratory. It is also something we can study to supply to our farmers. xxx	1. innovation in agriculture	1. Organic Farming Development	2. Language Patterns and Communication
SP Member 1: xxx We should also consider how many	2. organic integrity		

<p>cycles it takes to breed chickens until a pure breed is obtained. Therefore, we must study the process of seed regeneration (inaudible word) we aim to return the fruit to its organic state until we obtain a pure breed. xxx</p>			
<p>City Budget Officer: xxx it's important to appreciate organic products. xxx</p>	<p>3. appreciation of organic products</p>		
<p>City Budget Officer: xxx Perhaps that is the process that our City Agriculture should study so that we do not always buy new, xxx</p>	<p>4. sustainable practices</p>		
<p>Resource Person 1: xxx From my perspective on organic, because I have been trying organic farming for several years now, I am also using concoctions that I make on my farm. This wood vinegar can be used as a spray for plants. xxx</p>	<p>5. Personal experience with organic farming</p>		
<p>Resource Person 1: So now, in my planting of plants, vegetables, I am also using organic methods. Xxx</p>	<p>6. organic farming adoption</p>		
<p>Resource Person 2: xxx What happens is it ends up as pig feed because the ones from Davao look better, but</p>	<p>1. product spoilage</p>	<p>2. Supply Chain and Production Management</p>	

<p>these are organic. xxx</p> <p>Resource Person 3: xxx This makes it challenging for us banana farmers to market our produce, sometimes resorting to feeding them to pigs or goats. Xxx</p> <p>SP Member 1: xxx they are fed to pigs or given away, and that is what I consider truly organic, madam SP Chairperson.</p> <p>City Budget Officer: xxx what happens is they just keep producing products with no buyers, leading to spoilage. Sometimes, as the ladies say, it will just be fed to the pigs, xxx</p>			
<p>Resource Person 1: xxx So, that is if it comes from organic seeds, I do not know how the organic seeds will be supplied to us. So, perhaps we can be helped to be provided with organic seeds so we will no longer use the ones we buy from xxx</p>	<p>2. supply chain challenges</p>		

<p>City Agriculturist: The seeds we distribute are not organic but open-pollinated. When we say open-pollinated, it means that when it bears fruit, you can take seeds from it that will yield the same as the previous crop. The hybrid ones cannot be used for seeds because they are given for production purposes. xxx The open-pollinated ones are for backyard gardening.</p>	<p>3. seed type clarification</p>		
<p>City Agriculturist: No, it's not organic because it's a yellow corn hybrid, and there's a certain metric ton target for production.</p>	<p>4. hybrid seed production goals</p>		
<p>SP Member 2: When will it be possible, can you be certain as to when we can produce or provide organic seeds to farmers?</p>	<p>5. organic seed provision timeline</p>		
<p>City Agriculturist: We need to establish an endemic farm, yes, so that we can produce organic seeds.</p>	<p>6. initiative for organic seed farm establishment</p>		
<p>City Agriculturist: Three years, sir, because there is a certain time...</p>	<p>7. timeframe for establishment</p>		

<p>SP Member 2: xxx The draft ordinance may cost one million (1,000,000) initially, just the initial amount of 1,000,000 for the implementation of this ordinance subject to the annual allocation of such amount as may be deemed necessary. xxx</p>	<p>1. funding requirements and investment planning</p>	<p>3. Financial Planning and Resource Allocation</p>	
<p>City Budget Officer: I am not certain about the AIP, which is why I returned because as I said earlier, my answer would remain the same.</p>	<p>2. funding allocation uncertainty</p>		
<p>City Budget Officer: xxx So, it is possible to allocate funds from the appropriation because xxx</p>	<p>3. potential for fund reallocation</p>		
<p>City Budget Officer: xxx But for instance, if OCVAS also implements it as part of their program, it will become part of their annual appropriation and will no longer be specific for this purpose, it would be like it's over and above the appropriation of OCVAS.</p>	<p>4. institutional implementation and budget integration</p>		
<p>SP Member 2: xxx So, we need to identify if this is included in the</p>	<p>5. funding challenges</p>		

OCVAS program xxx			
<p>City Budget Officer: xxx because we do not have the funds that should also be provided by the barangay program.</p> <p>City Budget Officer: I am not certain about the AIP, xxx.</p> <p>City Budget Officer: xxx if the ordinance already includes a funding requirement for an initial fund, it will indeed be allocated there.</p>	6. funding allocation		
<p>City Budget Officer: xxx That's why I mentioned earlier that it is over and above the appropriation for OCVAS. Xxx they could do so upon the execution of the 2024 budget.</p>	7. OCVAS appropriation		
<p>City Budget Officer: xxx we will indeed allocate it with its own line, which we call line budgeting xxx</p>	8. line budgeting		
<p>City Budget Officer: xxx Now, they should also clarify in the process what is needed, what will be purchased, what should be paid for, xxx</p>	9. expenditure clarification		
<p>Resource Person 2: xxx You know, it is truly wonderful that</p>	10. budget allocation for organic projects		

<p>we are providing a budget particularly for this project, xxx</p>			
<p>SP Chairperson: xxx Over the years, our city government has implemented numerous agricultural programs, witnessing our city's high aspirations to further enhance and keep up with the challenges of the times in agricultural matters. xxx</p>	<p>1. historical progression and institutional commitment</p>		
<p>SP Chairperson: xxx This year, separate offices for City Agriculture and City Veterinary were established. xxx</p>	<p>2. organizational restructuring and specialization</p>		
<p>SP Chairperson: Thank you very much, Mrs. Flora Alvarez. That's why when we talked about the need to have an ordinance on organic farming, your servant indeed did research, I spoke with my fellow councilors if they could join us in passing this organic agriculture, right?</p>	<p>3. collaborative governance</p>	<p>1. Organizational Dynamics and Support Systems</p>	<p>3. Integration of R&D in Formulating Agricultural Ordinance</p>
<p>SP Chairperson: xxx I would like to hear from City Agriculturist, the OIC of the City Agriculturist, regarding your comments or suggestions on the</p>	<p>4. feedback mechanisms</p>		

draft of the Proposed Ordinance that I provided to you.			
SP Chairperson: The Committee Hearing on Agriculture is now called to order.	1. initiation of formal proceedings		
SP Chairperson: xxx The Committee Hearing on Agriculture is now called to order. Good morning to everyone, to our fellow councilors present here, before we start, I would like to recognize the guests who are here xxx	2. recognition of participants		
SP Chairperson: xxx We are here because of an ordinance that we need to pass, the Organic Agriculture Ordinance. I just want to remind everyone before we start, we have rules, anyone who has a concern or question shall be recognized first by the SP Chairperson, please state your name, your office, and designation first for record purposes. All questions must be addressed to the SP Chairperson, so that we can proceed more	3. agenda setting	2. Legislative Processes and Material Distribution	

<p>efficiently. I have given you copies, and my fellow councilors have been provided copies as well.</p>			
<p>SP Chairperson: xxx I just want to remind everyone before we start, we have rules, anyone who has a concern or question shall be recognized first by the SP Chairperson, please state your name, your office, and designation first for record purposes. All questions must be addressed to the SP Chairperson, so that we can proceed more efficiently.</p>	<p>4. rules of engagement</p>		
<p>SP Chairperson: xxx Therefore, I, your humble servant, along with my fellow councilors and members of the committee, have authored an ordinance xxx</p>	<p>5. legislative authorship</p>		
<p>City Agriculturist: I am Flora C. Alvarez from the Office of the City Agriculture, and this morning I stand before you to explain about the Implementing Rules and Regulation or R.A. 100068, also known as the</p>	<p>6. clarification, procedural formalities, and material distribution</p>		

<p>Organic Agriculture Act of 2010.</p> <p>Chair: You have no idea?</p> <p>SP Chairperson: Thank you very much, City Agriculturist.</p> <p>SP Chairperson: Thank you, City Agriculturist.</p> <p>SP Chairperson: xxx To our fellow city councilors, SP Member 1 is recognized. SP Member 1: Thank you, Honorable SP Chairperson. Xxx</p> <p>SP Chairperson: Thank you SP Member 1, SP Member 2 is now recognized.</p> <p>SP Chairperson: Thank you, City Agriculturist. Let us now listen to Resource Person 4. Sir, please state your name and designation.</p> <p>SP Chairperson: Thank you very much, City Budget</p>			
--	--	--	--

<p>Officer. SP Member 2 is recognized.</p> <p>SP Chairperson: xxx I have given you copies, and my fellow councilors have been provided copies as well.</p>			
<p>SP Member 2: xxx I'm acknowledging our becoming City Agriculturist to reach out to the barangay officials to consider this, as it is a very good program. xxx</p>	<p>1. outreach and engagement</p>	<p>3. Program Execution and Support</p>	
<p>SP Member 2: Okay, if I may continue, even if it's not in the AIP, the submissions by OCVAS can still be executed, though I think not.</p>	<p>2. operational flexibility</p>		
<p>City Budget Officer: xxx However, if we have leeway in the AIP, it's the AIP that will be entered, not our long-term projects, which can be implemented one by one, anytime.</p>	<p>3. AIP entry and project flexibility</p>		
<p>SP Chairperson: "Thank you, SP Member 2, that's true, if you talk there will be no problem for us, we can implement it, thank you."</p>	<p>4. optimism for implementation</p>		
<p>Resource Person 1: xxx the Department of Agriculture has built a small</p>	<p>5. Department of Agriculture support</p>		

<p>building on my farm where these concoctions are made, such as FFJ and amino phases. They also constructed a facility for producing wood vinegar, xxx</p>			
<p>Resource Person 1: xxx So, perhaps we can be helped to be provided with organic seeds so we will no longer use the ones we buy from... xxx</p>	<p>6. resources for organic farming</p>		
<p>SP Member 3: xxx there might be a misinterpretation that the technical committee and the council mentioned are different, that's it. And Madam SP Chairperson, regarding the functions provision, no.7, it is written here, the committee shall have the following functions, so we know the difference between shall and may, shall is stronger and since this is an ordinance it needs to be absolute and not negotiable.</p>	<p>1. clarity in legislation</p>	<p>4. Legislative Clarity and Framework</p>	
<p>SP Chairperson: xxx I just have a correction here, Ma'am Flor, in Article 2, Institutional Mechanism, Letter B, and Composition.</p>	<p>2. institutional mechanism amendments</p>		

SP Member 2: xxx Section 336 states that the budget is only for that purpose.	3. policy provisions for organic farming			
City Agriculturist: The city government will pay.	4. governmental support			
City Agriculturist: It comes from the national board, as there are certifying bodies.	5. institutional framework			
SP Member 1: So, you will endorse the product to the national level, and then they will determine if it's organic, they will issue the certificate and also collect the payment, how much do you think that would be?	6. procedural clarity			
City Budget Officer: xxx In my opinion, it seems the IDC is not included in the ordinance for people to appreciate the importance of organic produce.	7. inclusion of industrial development councils			
Resource Person 4: xxx I can say that this is significant for our fellow farmers, who we know regard farming as a livelihood and business. xxx	1. importance of ordinances for farmers			5. Organic Farming Legislation and Aspirations
Resource Person 4: xxx I believe that if this does not become an ordinance, it will be challenging to	2. challenges without a legal framework			

<p>implement. We have no problem; we understand, but explaining this to our fellow farmers might be difficult. Therefore, it is excellent that this will now become an ordinance. xxx</p>			
<p>Resource Person 4: xxx I am grateful because today, an ordinance on organic farming will be enacted. xxx</p>	<p>3. gratitude for enactment</p>		
<p>SP Chairperson: xxx We really want this matter to become an ordinance so that what we are discussing here can be experienced, that our food will be organic. xxx</p>	<p>4. legislative aspirations and organic food accessibility</p>		

The presentation of data is structured to reflect the nuanced exploration of knowledge, language patterns and communication, and the integration of R&D in policy formulation. These themes are pivotal in understanding the intricacies of legislative processes and the impact of research and development in policy-making. The data presented underwent coding process: a systematic approach of assigning descriptive labels to unique data elements in organizing and interpreting data. The coding process was pivotal in applying content analysis or the method of interpreting the meaning that can be derived from text data from classification and theme identification. Discourse analysis was also employed in the data by interpreting the contexts leading to construction of plausible meanings from the noted observations on the social

interactions as presented by the document. With the ethnomethodological approach, the shared social reality observed in the process of conducting committee hearing for the formulation of an organic ordinance in a city government was further interpreted by the study by employing knowledge flow process, thematic analysis, and theme generation.

1. Knowledge. Exploring the presence and integration of research and development (R&D) in local agricultural ordinance formulation is significantly enhanced with the theme 'role of forms of knowledge'. Knowledge can be generically categorized as (1) Scientific knowledge, for instance, informs evidence-based policy-making, ensuring that the ordinance is grounded in the latest agricultural research; (2) Local and indigenous knowledge, on the other hand, ensures that the ordinance is relevant and sensitive to the local context and practices; and (3) Collaborative knowledge created through the interaction between farmers, researchers, and policymakers can lead to more innovative. But to fully elaborate the discussion, Types of Knowledge (Gilanie, 2022) was adopted in the study discussion.

2. Language Patterns and Communication. The way language is used and understood within the legislative context is another theme that warrants careful dissection. The presentation dissected specific language patterns used in a committee hearing as extracted from the Journal of Proceedings, exploring how terminology, jargon, and discourse styles as observed in both local legislators and invited resource persons influence the understanding and outcomes of policy discussions. This theme presentation include transcripts of dialogues or

debates, annotated to show how communication styles either facilitate or hinder the policy formulation process.

3. Integration of R&D in Policy Formulation. With the presence of the identified themes role of forms of knowledge and language patterns and communications, R&D concepts were proven to be integrated in the local process of legislating agricultural policy. The identified themes were enough to prove that R&D, though subtly referenced, is composite to the formulated local agricultural ordinance.

Chapter V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to investigate the integration of R&D in the formulation of a local agricultural ordinance in the legislative department of a city government. The results obtained from the data analysis presented relevant insights that the roles of forms of knowledge and the language patterns and communications observed from the participant as reflected by the analysed documented information proved that R&D is integrated in local policy formulation of the research locale. This chapter further presents the discourses on the detailed accounts of excerpts where codes, sub-themes, and themes were generated.

Role of Forms of Knowledge

This theme explores how the different forms of knowledge are utilized, valued, and displayed by the stakeholders, as presented in the table. Though knowledge forms can be presented as scientific, experiential, or local, the researcher adopted the forms of knowledge published by Gulani in 2022.

Table 2

Type of Knowledge Classification from Generated Codes

Theme	Sub-theme	Code	Type of Knowledge
1. Role of forms of Knowledge	1. Certification and Regulation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. includes usage limits and safety concerns 2. organic certification uncertainty 3. budget considerations for organic certification 4. importance of certification for organic products 5. certification cost 6. timeframe for organic certification 7. requirements for organic certification 8. challenges in certification and seed origin 	Empirical Domain Encoded Conceptual Implicit Implicit Implicit Tacit
	2. Communication and Education	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. interdepartmental communication 2. information dissemination 3. educational integration of organic farming 4. observation of agricultural practices 5. verification of organic farming methods 	Imperative Descriptive Domain Empirical A Posteriori
	3. Community and Health	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. community practices and perceptions of organic produce 2. consumer preference and market progress 3. environmental advocacy 4. community health 5. current state of organic farming 	Tacit Empirical Domain Descriptive Tacit
	4. Environmental and Economic Impacts	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. environmental impact 2. economic impact 3. implementation of organic farming test and protection mechanisms for farming tests 4. current agricultural practices 	Empirical Domain Procedural Tacit
	5. Innovative Agricultural Practices	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. traditional knowledge 2. application of wood vinegar 3. organic waste management 4. local agricultural practices 5. organic farming adoption 6. organic farming test sites 7. organic farming certification and practices 	Tacit Empirical Empirical Domain Procedural Explicit Explicit

1. Role of Forms of Knowledge

1.1. Certification and Regulation

1.1.1. usage limits and safety concerns

SP Member 2: xxx The use of fertilizers, which contain chemical compositions, cannot be said to be safe, although there are certain limits on how to use them. xxx

Usage limits and safety concerns. This code emerges from SP Member 2's expressed caution regarding the use of fertilizers with chemical compositions. This statement highlighted the need for safe application practices of chemical compositions within prescribed limits. This statement is an evidence that SP Member 2 possesses an understanding and recognition of the importance of fertilizer application and the limitation or moderation that must be applied in farming practices.

From the cited statement, Empirical Knowledge is displayed as a form of knowledge. Empirical Knowledge is defined and said to be as a form of knowledge that is based on a person's experiences and observations derived in conduct of a certain practice.

1.1.2 organic certification uncertainty

SP Member 2: xxx At OCVAS, all the seeds we distribute, are you certain that those are organic?

The code organic certification uncertainty was generated from SP Member 2's query about the authenticity of the organic seeds distributed by OCVAS, reflecting a need for assurance in the organic quality of agricultural products. This uncertainty highlights the importance of clear communication and education regarding organic certification processes.

This involves knowledge that is specific to a particular field or domain, in this case, the certainty about the organic nature of seeds distributed by OCVAS. The text questions the organic nature of seeds, and can be linked to Domain (Expert) Knowledge, which is specialized knowledge within a particular area. The inquiry about the seeds' organic status suggests a need for expert understanding in agricultural practices and organic certification standards.

1.1.3 budget considerations for organic certification

*City Agriculturist: The budget is already
integrated into our ... xxx*

This refers to knowledge that has been formally documented or integrated, such as a budget. The statement, "The budget is already integrated," is an example of Encoded Knowledge, which is information that has been converted into textual, symbolic, or coded form to convey meaning, such as financial reports or budget plans.

1.1.4 importance of certification for organic products

City Agriculturist: It is necessary because for them to be called organic products or organically grown vegetables and fruits, there must be certifying bodies that will certify that they are organically grown.

"Budget considerations for organic certification" and "importance of certification for organic products," are codes that relate to the financial planning required to ensure organic products are certified, which is crucial for maintaining the integrity and trust in organic labeling.

As this statement expressed understanding of the concept of certification and its relationship the certification process itself, it can be classified under Conceptual Knowledge.

1.1.5 certification cost

City Agriculturist: What I hear is that certification alone costs sixty thousand (60,000) for a single product, plus there are other fees because many studies need to be conducted.

1.1.6 timeframe for organic certification

City Agriculturist: It takes several years before you can be granted certification because implementing

organic farming takes five (5) years before you can be certified as organic practitioners.

1.1.7 requirements for organic certification

City Agriculturist: What I hear is that certification alone costs sixty thousand (60,000) for a single product, plus there are other fees because many studies need to be conducted. It takes several years before you can be granted certification because implementing organic farming takes five (5) years before you can be certified as organic practitioners.

Certification cost is another code that refers to the high expense involved in certifying a single product as organic, which is a barrier for many farmers. This is correlated with the code 'timeframe for organic certification' as it indicates the lengthy process required to achieve certification, often taking several years due to the requirement that land must be farmed organically for a period before certification can be granted. For the code 'requirements for organic certification', it can be opined that additional elaboration on organic certification qualification must be conducted in order to secure compliance.

Hands-on experiences and direct observation results to the gaining of Implicit Knowledge. Along with time and observation, the City Agriculturist had gained knowledge in defining and elaborating the codes certification cost, timeframe for organic certification, and requirements for organic certification. The Implicit Knowledge the City

Agriculturist displayed is a combination of direct experiences and observations that provided nuanced perspective on the said codes.

1.1.8 challenges in certification and seed origin

City Agriculturist: xxx However, the seeds they use are not endemic, they are not hybrid, xxx but that's an assumption because they are not yet certified. xxx but we cannot say they are organic because there are no certifying bodies to certify them.

Challenges in certification and seed origin. The excerpt cited from the City Agriculturist presented issues in obtaining organic certification if the seeds. There are queries on how to prove if the seeds are endemic or hybrid due to lack of certification. Thus, organic certification is opined to start with seed origin certification.

As insights and intuitions become the basis of declaring if a seed is organic or not, and considering that certification from certifying bodies are not present, Tacit Knowledge can be assigned as the form of knowledge that is derived from the provided excerpt.

The enumerated forms of knowledge: Empirical, Domain (Expert), Encoded, Implicit, and Tacit; plays a crucial involvement for the relevant stakeholders' understanding on the subtleties presented by the sub-theme Certification and Regulation. Evidences, technical expertise, innate procedural understanding or knowledge, understanding on regulatory compliances, and personal and direct experiences are knowledge that compliments the formulation of an agricultural ordinance. These are vital in coming up with an informed decision.

1.2 Communication and Education

1.2.1 interdepartmental communication

SP Member 2: xxx it won't proceed unless you have communication with our good City Budget Officer and discuss it thoroughly. Xxx

Interdepartmental communication is the code drawn from the importance on the need of dialogue with the City Budget Officer to advance certain proceedings, highlighting the importance of cross-departmental partnership for effective governance and enactment of agricultural policies.

The text discusses the inevitability of communication with the City Budget Officer, can be associated with Imperative Knowledge. This type of knowledge is procedural and focuses on the 'how-to' aspect of knowledge, stressing the process and steps required to achieve a particular goal. In this case, the knowledge pertains to the procedural steps necessary for progressing a project or initiative within a department.

1.2.2 information dissemination

SP Chairperson: Thank you, Mr. Zalada, what we have heard is very educational for us, we have only heard about it now, xxx

Information dissemination is the code inferred from the SP Chairperson's acknowledgment of the educational value of the information presented and Resource Person 2's advocacy for widespread information sharing. This emphasizes the role of

education in empowering the majority with the knowledge required for informed decision-making in agricultural practices.

The text where the SP Chairperson recognizes the educational value of the information received, relates to Descriptive Knowledge. This form of knowledge encompasses understanding and conveying observations about the world. It is evident here as the Chairperson has learned something new and describes the information as educational.

1.2.3 educational integration of organic farming

SP Member 1: Madam SP Chairperson. Let's promote our Organic Farming in schools.

SP Member 2: xxx So, maybe as soon as possible we should educate them, teach them the correct process so we can get started. Because if we wait for the right time, I might not get to taste organic food anymore. But we should start as soon as possible to realize and implement this, thank you.

Educational integration of organic farming is a code based on SP Member 1's proposal to endorse organic farming within educational institutions. This proposal directs a strategic approach to include organic farming knowledge in the curriculum, by this means raising an informed future generation about sustainable agricultural practices.

The text advocating for the promotion of Organic Farming in schools, aligns with Domain (Expert) Knowledge. This is specialized knowledge within a particular field, in

this instance, the integration of organic farming into educational curricula. The call for immediate education on organic farming processes further underscores the need for domain-specific knowledge that is both practical and applicable.

1.2.4 observation of agricultural practices

SP Member 1: xxx. So, I just want to ask what is being watered on the plants.

Observation of agricultural practices is a code that likely stems from the inquiry about what substances are being applied to the plants. This suggests a need to observe and understand the farming practices in place.

The text which is an inquiry about agricultural practices, can be linked to Empirical Knowledge. This type of knowledge is based on observation and experience, mainly through the senses. The question about what is being watered on the plants search for empirical evidence to understand the practice better.

1.2.5 verification of organic farming methods

SP Member 1: That's what is being watered?

Verification of organic farming methods as a code parallels to the follow-up question from SP Member 1, which proposes a need for verification or proof of the organic farming methods being employed.

The text that questions the methods used in organic farming, can be linked with A Posteriori Knowledge. This knowledge is consequential from experience or empirical evidence. The inquiry about the substance being used for watering plants shows a search for knowledge that comes from direct observation or experience.

The forms of knowledge generated from the presented codes under the sub-theme Communication and Education are procedural, descriptive, domain specific, empirical, and experiential. These forms of knowledge is not just purposeful, but, essential in the process of formulating an agricultural ordinance.

The code interdepartmental communication emphasizes the innate understanding existing between the transacting departments that are involved in the formulation of a local agricultural ordinance. For this study, the departments involved are the legislative department, the city budget office, and the city agriculture office. The involvement are all important as the provisions are based on the agricultural needs of the city and the capacity of the city to fund the programs associated in the implementation of the agricultural ordinance. Having an established communication between the involved city government departments ensures the formulation and implementation of its ordinances.

Information dissemination is a code generated that underscores the relevance of a process of transferring knowledge to the involved stakeholders in a city government. With the transferred knowledge, parties arrived in an informed decision. On the other hand, the code educational integration of organic farming reflects a proactive initiative of the legislative department and its local legislators of coming up with an action of including organic agriculture in the city's education curriculum for the purpose of further promoting the use of organic agriculture. This is vital in the promotion and management of knowledge.

Observation of agricultural practices is a code generated where organic-related agricultural practices are already being applied and utilized by the local farmers involved even in the absence of a certifying body. Their experiences are inevitably proves that knowledge in agricultural practices as observed, are transferred.

The 'verification of organic farming methods' code suggests an authentication procedure that goes beyond theoretical knowledge, demanding a hands-on approach to determine the authenticity and effectiveness of organic farming practices. This verification is a form of knowledge application, where the proof lies in the practical demonstration of methods.

These codes mutually exemplify the complex connection between knowledge and the sub-theme of 'Communication and Education.' They emphasize the central role of knowledge in agriculture, where effective communication, education, and practical application come together to advance the sector's development and ensure its sustainability.

1.3 Community and Health

1.3.1 community practices and perceptions of organic produce

SP Member 1: The Lakatan bananas are very delicious, xxx and that is what I consider truly organic, madam SP Chairperson.

The code, 'community practices and perceptions of organic produce,' is derived from the same member's remarks on the organic nature of Lakatan bananas and their consumption, whether sold, fed to pigs, or given away. This statement points to a broader understanding and recognition of organic produce within the community, as well as the practices that support its sustainability.

The text which discusses community practices and perceptions of organic produce, can be related with Tacit Knowledge. This type of knowledge is personal,

context-specific, and often hard to formalize and communicate. The SP Member's statement reveals subjective experience and personal judgment about what constitutes 'truly organic,' which aligns with the nature of Tacit Knowledge.

1.3.2 consumer preference and market progress

City Budget Officer: xxx The problem will be with the buyers; the product is there, it may not be certified but we believe some things are organic because they are obtained organically. However, as long as consumers do not appreciate the value of organic produce, our products will not progress because we still prefer to buy even if the Melon has a slight blemish, although it's not deep, it's just on the surface, but we still won't buy it, we will still choose the perfectly smooth melon. The same goes for bananas, eggplants, okra. What's important is, for example, if the okra is much curved, it might be organic but no one will buy such curved okra.

The code, 'consumer preference and market progress,' is derived from the City Budget Officer's opinion of consumer behavior towards organic produce. He notes the challenges faced by organic products in the market due to consumer preferences for aesthetically perfect produce, despite minor blemishes being superficial.

The text regarding consumer preference and market progress, demonstrates Empirical Knowledge. This knowledge is grounded on observations and experiences,

particularly concerning consumer behavior and market dynamics. The City Budget Officer's comments about consumer choices and the marketability of organic products, despite their appearance, are based in empirical observations of buying patterns.

1.3.3 environmental advocacy

City Agriculturist: xxx The truth is, our office advocates for the implementation of organic farming here in the City of Batangas. xxx

The code, "environmental advocacy," is obvious in the commitment to promoting organic farming practices within Batangas, reflecting a dedication to sustainable agricultural methods.

The text which is a statement from the City Agriculturist on environmental advocacy, denotes Domain (Expert) Knowledge. This knowledge is explicit to a particular area or domain, in this case, agriculture and environmental practices. The advocacy for organic farming in study locale by a professional in the field is a clear example of Domain Knowledge, as it is based on expertise and specialized understanding.

1.3.4 community health

City Agriculturist: xxx can produce healthy and nutritious fruits and vegetables, thus greatly benefiting human health, xxx

The code, "community health," is linked to the assertion that organic produce can lead to better health outcomes for consumers, thereby connecting agricultural practices directly to the well-being of the community.

The text from the City Agriculturist relates to community health and can be linked to Descriptive Knowledge. This type of knowledge involves descriptions of the world and can include facts, information, and descriptions of "how things are." The statement about the health benefits of consuming organic produce is descriptive, providing information on the positive impacts of organic farming on human health.

1.3.5 current state of organic farming

Resource Person 2: xxx but now we have so many organic farmers who actually do not know that they are organic farmers. xxx

The local farmers are naturally inclined to organic methods, though these methods are not formally certified, recognized, and labelled as organic. This is the data generated from the code current state of organic farming, as noted from Resource Person 2's observation.

Addressing the current state of organic farming in the locale of the study suggests Tacit Knowledge. The unlabelled, uncertified, and unrecognized application of organic farming methods as shared in the community denotes a widespread common practice.

In summary, the codes derived from a number of observations within the study locale reveal a community rich in knowledge concerning organic farming and its

implications. This knowledge, while not always codified or explicitly taught, permeates the community's approach to health, the environment, and the economy, shaping a sustainable way of life that honors the intrinsic value of organic methods and produce. It is this knowledge that supports the community's resilience and adaptability, guaranteeing the continuity of practices that are beneficial for both people and the planet.

1.4 Environmental and Economic Impacts

1.4.1 environmental impact

City Agriculturist: xxx So, what we will use are natural resources, organic fertilizers from plant and animal waste, which pose minimal risk to the environment, xxx avoiding the destruction of natural habitats or natural resources. The use of chemicals causes the destruction of the ecology or biodiversity of our environment. xxx

Environmental impact code is derived from the difference between the minimal risk posed by organic farming and the significant ecological damage caused by chemical fertilizers, underlining the importance of preserving biodiversity and natural habitats.

The text discussing the environmental impact of using natural resources and organic fertilizers, denotes Empirical Knowledge. This type of knowledge is established on observations and experiences, particularly regarding the minimal risk to the environment and the adverse effects of chemicals on ecology and biodiversity. It is a

form of knowledge derived from sensory experience as opposed to theoretical knowledge.

1.4.2 economic impact

City Agriculturist: Therefore, this ordinance will be a great help if implemented here in our City of Batangas, it will also help farmers to be safe from the harmful effects of chemicals and then provide additional income for the farmers.

Economic impact is a code associated with the potential for organic farming to provide additional income for farmers, signifying that sustainable practices can also be economically viable.

The text which addresses the economic impact of an ordinance on farmers, can be associated with Domain (Expert) Knowledge. This knowledge is definite to a particular area, in this case, the economic domain, where the agriculturist predicts the ordinance's beneficial outcomes based on expertise and understanding of the subject matter.

1.4.3 implementation of organic farming test and protection mechanisms for farming tests

SP Member 1: xxx but do we have identified locations and a mechanism to protect the said farming test?

The 'implementation of organic farming test and protection mechanisms for farming tests' code proposes that there is an ongoing effort to establish organic farming practices, but there is also a need for mechanisms to safeguard these tests, ensuring their integrity and the reliability of the results.

The text that questions the implementation of organic farming tests and protection mechanisms, is an example of Procedural Knowledge, also known as Imperative Knowledge. It concerns the methods and processes involved in implementing and protecting farming tests, indicating a practical understanding of the steps required to achieve a specific goal.

1.4.4 current agricultural practices

City Agriculturist: Currently, sir, since 2000 we have implemented farming, but we cannot say it is totally organically grown because they use hybrid seeds and organic fertilizers, including organic foliar fertilizer.

The 'current agricultural practices' code reflects the reality that, despite efforts to implement organic methods, the use of hybrid seeds and organic fertilizers does not fully meet the criteria for organic farming, thus preventing full certification.

The text which speaks to the current agricultural practices, reflects Tacit Knowledge. This is the kind of knowledge that is difficult to transfer to another person by

writing it down or verbalizing it. It's the know-how accumulated over the years, as indicated by the agriculturist's reference to practices since 2000 and the nuanced understanding of what constitutes 'totally organically grown' produce.

Each text exemplifies a distinct form of knowledge, from empirical observations of environmental impacts to the expert economic analysis, procedural details of implementing farming tests, and the tacit knowledge inherent in ongoing agricultural practices. These forms of knowledge are crucial in understanding and addressing the multifaceted aspects of agriculture and its impacts on both the environment and the economy.

In summary, knowledge is the core upon which sustainable agricultural practices are built, influencing both environmental integrity and economic sustainability. It is the silent partner in the formulation of an organic ordinance the locale of the study.

1.5 Innovative Agricultural Practices

1.5.1 traditional knowledge

City Budget Officer: xxx there is another way like in the fields when the first harvest of corn is aged and then placed behind the granary to be sun-dried, which is what is used for planting, xxx

City Budget Officer: xxx since I grew up on our island where those seeds were really hung behind the granary, and every rainy season, that is what will be sorted by the mothers and then planted again in the fields. Xxx

The code, 'traditional knowledge,' is drawn from the City Budget Officer reference to ancestral methods of seed preservation and planting. This emphasizes the value of indigenous knowledge and practices that have been passed down through generations, which can offer sustainable alternatives to modern methods.

The text that discusses traditional methods of selecting and sun-drying corn for planting, exemplifies 'Tacit Knowledge,' which is knowledge acquired through personal experience and often difficult to articulate or transfer to others. This type of knowledge is deeply associated in local customs and practices, passed down through generations, and is vital to maintaining biodiversity in employing agricultural practices.

1.5.2 application of wood vinegar

Resource Person 1: xxx This wood is burned in a chamber, and the resulting liquid is the wood vinegar. I am already using these methods.

Resource Person 1's use of wood vinegar from burned wood as a plant spray is an example of practical R&D application in agriculture, proving how traditional knowledge and modern techniques can be merged to create innovative solutions.

1.5.3 organic waste management

Resource Person 1: In the composting facility, that's what I use for quick decomposition when I water it on my accumulated grass or remaining waste in the field, the wood vinegar decomposes quickly, xxx.

The code, 'organic waste management,' is denoted from the use of wood vinegar in the composting facility to accelerate the decomposition of grass and agricultural waste, presenting a sustainable practice of managing farm by-products.

Application of wood vinegar and organic waste management represent 'Empirical Knowledge,' derived from observation and experimentation. This knowledge is practical and often forms the basis for innovative applications in sustainable agriculture.

1.5.4 local agricultural practices

Resource Person 1: So, what I did before with a drum of water, that's the foliar that serves as a bloom booster fertilizer for the plants.

The code 'local agricultural practices,' are based on Resource Person 1's use of homemade concoctions and wood vinegar, which he applies for quick decomposition of organic waste and as a bloom booster fertilizer. These practices reflect a hands-on, innovative, and localized approach to farming that maximizes the use of on-site resources.

The text that details the use of a water drum as a bloom booster, is an example of 'Domain (Expert) Knowledge,' where specific expertise is applied to enhance agricultural productivity.

1.5.5 organic farming adoption

Resource Person 1: So now, in my planting of plants, vegetables, I am also using organic methods.

Xxx

The code, 'organic farming adoption,' is evident in Resource Person 1's statement about his use of organic methods in planting vegetables, indicating a personal shift towards sustainable agricultural practices.

The text on the adoption of organic farming methods, illustrates 'Procedural Knowledge,' which involves knowing how to carry out a series of actions to achieve a desired outcome, in this case, sustainable cultivation of plants and vegetables.

1.5.6 organic farming test sites

SP Member 1: xxx Do you know of any locations where we can conduct an organic farming test?

The 'organic farming test sites' code points to inquiries about potential locations where organic farming methods can be tested, indicating a proactive search for suitable environments to further organic agriculture. It also indicates the search for suitable locations to conduct organic farming experiments, which is important for the practical assessment of organic farming methods.

1.5.7 organic farming certification and practices

City Agriculturist: What we have at OCVAS farming is organically grown, we just don't claim it unless certified.

The code 'organic farming certification and practices' is derived from City Agriculturist's statement about the organic nature of their farming, but also the significance of certification to make such a claim official.

'Organic farming test sites' and 'organic farming certification and practices' codes reflect 'Explicit Knowledge,' which is codified and communicated through formal language, documents, and procedures. This knowledge is necessary for the standardization and validation of organic farming practices, warranting that they meet established criteria for certification.

Each of these knowledge types contributes to the crucial role in the development and dissemination of innovative agricultural practices, backing to the sustainability and resilience of food systems.

The provided discussion underscores the importance of various knowledge types in agriculture, as derived and interpreted from the selected excerpts bearing the theme 'Role of Knowledge'. These include empirical, domain, encoded, conceptual, a posteriori, tacit, imperative, descriptive, domain, dispersed, procedural, explicit knowledge. The agricultural knowledge possessed by the stakeholders, as noted directly from the Journal of Proceedings, are not only a mere collection of evidences of knowledge but a

knowledge shaped in the community. It guides them as a silent voice that influences one's decision-making.

Language Patterns and Communication

Language patterns and communication are both treated a significant themes that promotes dissemination and comprehension of the integration of R&D in the formulation of a local agricultural ordinance in the legislative department of a city government. As a second theme of the study, language patterns and communication as observed and reflected from the analysed documented information draws the line of R&D integration in the formulation of local policy. It also considers the impact of communication strategies on the effectiveness of policy-making, emphasizing the need for clarity and precision in conveying complex R&D ideas.

2. Language Patterns and Communication

2.1. Organic Farming Development

2.1.1. innovation in agriculture

Resource Person 3: xxx Ma'am, regarding the tissue culture like the one at UP, it is available, but it seems not yet here... We have sometimes acquired it from UP. Tissue culture is done in a laboratory. It is also something we can study to supply to our farmers. xxx

Tissue culture, as mentioned by Resource Person 3, represents a scientific advancement that can be leveraged to enhance crop production and supply, which aligns with the code of innovation in agriculture.

2.1.2. organic integrity

SP Member 1: xxx We should also consider how many cycles it takes to breed chickens until a pure breed is obtained. Therefore, we must study the process of seed regeneration (inaudible word) we aim to return the fruit to its organic state until we obtain a pure breed. xxx

The discussion on breeding chickens for pure breeds and seed regeneration by SP Member 1 underscores the importance of maintaining organic integrity, ensuring that agricultural practices do not compromise the natural quality of produce.

2.1.3. appreciation of organic products

City Budget Officer: xxx it's important to appreciate organic products. Xxx

2.1.4. sustainable practices

City Budget Officer: xxx Perhaps that is the process that our City Agriculture should study so that we do not always buy new, xxx

City Budget Officer's emphasis on the significance of appreciating organic products reflects a growing consumer awareness and demand for sustainably produced goods. This is further reinforced by Resource Person 1's personal testimony of using organic methods and concoctions, which exemplifies sustainable practices that minimize environmental impact while maintaining farm productivity.

2.1.5. personal experience with organic farming

Resource Person 1: xxx From my perspective on organic, because I have been trying organic farming for several years now, I am also using concoctions that I make on my farm. This wood vinegar can be used as a spray for plants. xxx

2.1.6. organic farming adoption

Resource Person 1: So now, in my planting of plants, vegetables, I am also using organic methods.

Xxx

The adoption of organic farming methods, as shared by Resource Person 1 demonstrate a community's engagement with and perception of organic produce.

The excerpts or statements provided contributes to the discussion of the sub-theme in a collective manner. These highlight the stakeholders' commitment to the agricultural practices that are innovative and vital for the adoption of an organic

agricultural system. The sub-theme Organic Farming Development was generated from the codes innovation in agriculture, organic integrity, appreciation of organic products, sustainable practices, personal experience with organic farming, and organic farming adoption.

The sub-theme and codes reveals a complex yet powerful language patterns and communication that supports the exploration of discovering the integration of R&D in the local agricultural ordinance being developed by the city government through its legislative department. Though R&D is not explicitly and directly identified and is only referenced, the language patterns and communication conveyed emphasis on actions that promotes agriculture improvement and innovation in the locale. The synthesis of these codes under the general theme reflects a holistic view of organic farming as a dynamic, integrated system that evolves through conversation, collaboration, and commitment to core values.

2.2. Supply Chain and Production Management

2.2.1. product spoilage

Resource Person 2: xxx What happens is it ends up as pig feed because the ones from Davao look better, but these are organic. xxx

Resource Person 3: xxx This makes it challenging for us banana farmers to market our produce, sometimes resorting to feeding them to pigs or goats. xxx

SP Member 1: xxx they are fed to pigs or given away, and that is what I consider truly organic, madam SP Chairperson.

City Budget Officer: xxx what happens is they just keep producing products with no buyers, leading to spoilage. Sometimes, as the ladies say, it will just be fed to the pigs, xxx

The code 'product spoilage' emerges from the recurring issue of unsold organic produce resulting in spoilage or being used as animal feed, as mentioned by Resource Person 2, Resource Person 3, SP Member 1, and City Budget Officer. This indicates a gap in effective product management where the supply exceeds market demand, leading to wastage.

2.2.2. supply chain challenges

Resource Person 1: xxx So, that is if it comes from organic seeds, I do not know how the organic seeds will be supplied to us. So, perhaps we can be helped to be provided with organic seeds so we will no longer use the ones we buy from xxx

The 'supply chain challenges' code is reflected in the difficulty of marketing organic produce and the uncertainty about the provision of organic seeds, as expressed by

Resource Person 1. This points to a need for better coordination and support in the supply chain to ensure that organic farmers have access to necessary resources.

2.2.3. seed type clarification

City Agriculturist: The seeds we distribute are not organic but open-pollinated. When we say open-pollinated, it means that when it bears fruit, you can take seeds from it that will yield the same as the previous crop. The hybrid ones cannot be used for seeds because they are given for production purposes. xxx The open-pollinated ones are for backyard gardening.

The 'seed type clarification' is a code derived from City Agriculturist's explanation of the difference between organic and open-pollinated seeds, which underscores the importance of understanding seed types for quality control and sustainable farming practices.

2.2.4. hybrid seed production goals

City Agriculturist: No, it's not organic because it's a yellow corn hybrid, and there's a certain metric ton target for production.

The code 'hybrid seed production goals' reflects the balance between the demand for high-yield crops and the pursuit of organic farming methods. It acknowledges the current reliance on hybrid seeds to meet production targets while also hinting at the potential shift towards organic practices.

2.2.5. organic seed provision timeline

SP Member 2: When will it be possible, can you be certain as to when we can produce or provide organic seeds to farmers?

'Organic seed provision timeline' addresses the temporal aspect of transitioning to organic farming, indicating a period necessary for such a change to materialize. This code is crucial as it sets realistic expectations for the availability of organic seeds to farmers.

2.2.6. initiative for organic seed farm establishment

City Agriculturist: We need to establish an endemic farm, yes, so that we can produce organic seeds.

The desire and necessity of establishing an endemic farm that would result to the production of organic seed, as expressed by the City Agriculturist, is the basis for the

generation of the code 'initiative for organic seed farm establishment.' The desire and necessity is vital in the promotion of a sustainable agricultural practice. This is also reflect the commitment of the legislative department of considering this statement in the process of policy formulation.

2.2.7. timeframe for establishment

City Agriculturist: Three years, sir, because there is a certain time...

Along with the desire and necessity of establishing an endemic farm is the timeframe aspect for such establishment. Thus, the code 'timeframe for establishment' is generated. The expression of three years reflects a concrete period or number of years for the establishment of the endemic farm.

From the presented sub-theme Supply Chain and Production Management, the codes that were generated are the following: (1) product spoilage; (2) supply chain challenges; (3) seed type clarification; (4) hybrid seed production goals; (5) organic seed provision timeline; (6) initiative for organic seed farm establishment; and (7) timeframe for establishment.

2.3. Financial Planning and Resource Allocation

2.3.1. funding requirements and investment planning

SP Member 2: xxx The draft ordinance may cost one million (1,000,000) initially, just the initial amount of 1,000,000 for the implementation of this ordinance subject to the annual allocation of such amount as may be deemed necessary. xxx

The code, 'funding requirements and investment planning,' is evident in the mention of the draft ordinance's initial cost and the need for annual allocations, highlighting the necessity for careful financial planning and the establishment of funding prerequisites.

2.3.2. funding allocation uncertainty

City Budget Officer: I am not certain about the AIP, which is why I returned because as I said earlier, my answer would remain the same.

The code, 'funding allocation uncertainty,' is reflected in City Budget Officer's uncertainty about the Annual Investment Plan (AIP), indicating a lack of clarity in fund distribution.

2.3.3. potential for fund reallocation

City Budget Officer: xxx So, it is possible to allocate funds from the appropriation because xxx

The code, 'potential for fund reallocation,' is suggested by the possibility of funds being appropriated from one program to another, as mentioned in the context of OCVAS's annual appropriation.

2.3.4. institutional implementation and budget integration

City Budget Officer: xxx But for instance, if OCVAS also implements it as part of their program, it will become part of their annual appropriation and will no longer be specific for this purpose, it would be like it's over and above the appropriation of OCVAS.

The code, 'institutional implementation and budget integration,' is implied through the discussion of integrating the ordinance's implementation within OCVAS's existing budget, pointing to the need for institutional financial strategies that accommodate new initiatives.

2.3.5. funding challenges

SP Member 2: xxx So, we need to identify if this is included in the OCVAS program xxx

The code, 'funding challenges,' is inferred from the concern about identifying whether the ordinance is included in OCVAS's program and the acknowledgment of financial constraints, such as the lack of funds from the barangay program.

2.3.6. funding allocation

City Budget Officer: xxx because we do not have the funds that should also be provided by the barangay program.

City Budget Officer: I am not certain about the AIP, xxx.

City Budget Officer: xxx if the ordinance already includes a funding requirement for an initial fund, it will indeed be allocated there.

The code, 'funding allocation,' is derived from the final statement about the certainty of fund allocation if the ordinance stipulates an initial funding requirement.

2.3.7. OCVAS appropriation

City Budget Officer: xxx That's why I mentioned earlier that it is over and above the appropriation for OCVAS. Xxx they could do so upon the execution of the 2024 budget.

The code 'OCVAS appropriation' refers to the additional funds allocated for the Office of the City Veterinary and Agricultural Services, indicating a prioritization of resources for agricultural services.

2.3.8. line budgeting

City Budget Officer: xxx we will indeed allocate it with its own line, which we call line budgeting xxx

'Line budgeting' suggests a transparent and itemized approach to budgeting, where funds are allocated to specific lines or items, allowing for clear tracking and accountability.

2.3.9. expenditure clarification

City Budget Officer: xxx Now, they should also clarify in the process what is needed, what will be purchased, what should be paid for, xxx

'Expenditure clarification' emphasizes the need for detailed understanding and communication about what the budget will cover, including the items to be purchased and the expenses to be paid.

2.3.10. budget allocation for organic projects

Resource Person 2: xxx You know, it is truly wonderful that we are providing a budget particularly for this project, xxx

Lastly, 'budget allocation for organic projects' points to a dedicated funding stream for organic agriculture, which is a growing sector that requires specific financial support due to its unique practices and inputs.

In the context of formulating an agricultural ordinance, the sub-theme of Financial Planning and Resource Allocation encompasses a broad spectrum of considerations. Language patterns and communication were reflected from the generated codes: (1) funding requirements and investment planning; (2) funding allocation uncertainty; (3) potential for fund reallocation; (4) institutional implementation and budget integration; (5) funding challenges; (6) funding allocation; (7) OCVAS appropriation; (8) line budgeting; (9) expenditure clarification; and (10) budget allocation for organic projects.

The distinct language patterns and communication as expressed and directly quoted from the resource persons are presented in a tabular format below.

Table 3

Source of Statement of Generated Codes

Theme	Sub-theme	Code	Source of Statement
2. Language patterns and communication	1. Organic Farming Development	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. innovation in agriculture 2. organic integrity 3. appreciation of organic products 4. sustainable practices 5. personal experience with organic farming 6. organic farming adoption 	RP3 SPM1 CBO CBO RP1 RP1
	2. Supply Chain and Production Management	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. product spoilage 2. supply chain challenges 3. seed type clarification 4. hybrid seed production goals 5. organic seed provision timeline 6. initiative for organic seed farm establishment 7. timeframe for establishment 	RP2, RP3, SPM1, CBO RP1 CA CA SPM2 CA
	3. Financial Planning and Resource Allocation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. funding requirements and investment planning 2. funding allocation uncertainty 3. potential for fund reallocation 4. institutional implementation and budget integration 5. funding challenges 6. funding allocation 7. OCVAS appropriation 8. line budgeting 9. expenditure clarification 10. budget allocation for organic projects 	SPM2 CBO CBO CBO CBO CBO RP2
Source Codes RP: Resource Person SPM: Local Legislator CBO: City Budget Officer CA: City Agriculturist			

The iterative analysis of the Journal of Proceedings, as employed by the researcher, lead to the discovery of language patterns and communications that relates the subtle presence of R&D in the process of local legislation of a public policy. The generated codes under this sub-theme presented a narrative vital to the shaping and formulation of the proposed organic agriculture ordinance. Language patterns were generated as words were repeated frequently from the analysed journal of proceedings.

Integration of R&D Formulating Agricultural Ordinances

With the use of an ethnomethodological approach in exploring the integration of R&D in the legislative process of formulating local ordinance, the researcher had observed and noted the day-to-day interactions and methodical practices of the local legislators and the involved resource persons. The sense the sources of proofs, that even though R&D is subtly referenced, still, it is integrated in such legislative -process of -policy formulation. The observed social constructs, in form of expressed language patterns and communication and displaying of various forms of knowledge, R&D evidences were underscored despite of the absence of direct statements in the documented narrative. This section reveals the implicit yet crucial and impactful presence of R&D concepts, insights, and evidences in the legislative process.

3. Integration of R&D in Formulating Agricultural Ordinance

3.1. Organizational Dynamics and Support Systems

3.1.1. historical progression and institutional commitment

SP Chairperson: xxx Over the years, our city government has implemented numerous agricultural programs, witnessing our city's high aspirations to further enhance and keep up with the challenges of the times in agricultural matters. Xxx

With the city's long years of implementing agricultural programs, a sustained dedication and commitment that enhances agricultural practices over time can be opined and can be coded as 'historical progression and institutional commitment'. This statement is significant and is backed up by the ongoing formulation of an organic agricultural ordinance. In the past, the city government has been implementing agricultural-related and agricultural-promoting ordinances in the city but the formulation of an organic agriculture ordinance is a proof of new innovations.

3.1.2. organizational restructuring

SP Chairperson: xxx This year, separate offices for City Agriculture and City Veterinary were established. xxx

In 2024, the city government separated the then Office of the City Veterinary and Agriculture Services into standalone offices of the City Agriculture and the City Veterinary. It can be opined that this institutional movement shows an adaption towards the provision of a more focused and centered service in the different disciplines of veterinary-related and agriculture-related services and programs. Thus, the code organizational structuring is generated for this management mechanism.

3.1.3. collaborative governance

SP Chairperson: Thank you very much, Mrs. Flora Alvarez. That's why when we talked about the

need to have an ordinance on organic farming, your servant indeed did research, I spoke with my fellow councilors if they could join us in passing this organic agriculture, right?

The code collaborative governance was generated from this statement. The chairperson initiated an understanding and support among his/her fellow local legislators in the quest of lobbying, formulating, and enacting an organic agriculture ordinance. It was also expressed by the chairperson that a prior research study was conducted before the drafting of the ordinance. This is viewed by the researcher as a collaborative one in the parlance of local governance for it is a usual practice that legislators seek support among its colleagues in order for a local policy be enacted.

3.1.4. feedback mechanisms

SP Chairperson: xxx I would like to hear from City Agriculturist, the OIC of the City Agriculturist, regarding your comments or suggestions on the draft of the Proposed Ordinance that I provided to you.

This code was generated from the statement of the Chairperson airing or soliciting feedback from the resource person, the City Agriculturist. For a local policy to be refined and to assure that the provisions of such local ordinance is responsive to the needs of

the community, and also, advocates innovation and sustainability, feedbacks are necessary tools that facilitates revision and enhancement. It is just and fitting that a city agriculturist be solicited with such feedback as the expertise and skills a city agriculturist has is impactful in the formulation of a local agricultural ordinance.

Thus, the codes presented: historical progression and institutional commitment, organizational restructuring, collaborative governance, and feedback mechanism are codes that when grouped leads to the formulation of the sub-theme Organizational Dynamics and Support Systems.

3.2. Legislative Processes and Material Distribution

3.2.1. initiation of formal proceedings

*SP Chairperson: The Committee Hearing on
Agriculture is now called to order.*

The 'initiation of formal proceedings' code reflects the procedural start of a legislative session, where the SP Chairperson calls the meeting to order, signifying the commencement of official business.

3.2.2. recognition of participants

*SP Chairperson: xxx The Committee Hearing on
Agriculture is now called to order. Good morning to
everyone, to our fellow councilors present here, before*

we start, I would like to recognize the guests who are here xxx

The 'recognition of participants' code emphasizes the importance of acknowledging the presence and roles of those involved, fostering an inclusive environment for discussion.

3.2.3. agenda setting

SP Chairperson: xxx We are here because of an ordinance that we need to pass, the Organic Agriculture Ordinance. I just want to remind everyone before we start, we have rules, anyone who has a concern or question shall be recognized first by the SP Chairperson, please state your name, your office, and designation first for record purposes. All questions must be addressed to the SP Chairperson, so that we can proceed more efficiently. I have given you copies, and my fellow councilors have been provided copies as well.

'Agenda setting' indicates the SP Chairperson's role in outlining the topics for deliberation, in this case, the Organic Agriculture Ordinance, which sets a focused trajectory for the session.

3.2.4. rules of engagement

SP Chairperson: xxx I just want to remind everyone before we start, we have rules, anyone who has a concern or question shall be recognized first by the SP Chairperson, please state your name, your office, and designation first for record purposes. All questions must be addressed to the SP Chairperson, so that we can proceed more efficiently.

The 'rules of engagement' code establishes the protocol for interaction, ensuring orderly conduct and efficient progression of the meeting by directing questions through the SP Chairperson.

3.2.5. legislative authorship

SP Chairperson: xxx Therefore, I, your humble servant, along with my fellow councilors and members of the committee, have authored an ordinance xxx

'Legislative authorship' signifies the collaborative effort in drafting legislation, highlighting the collective responsibility and contribution of the councilors and committee members.

3.2.6. clarification, procedural formalities, and material distribution

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: I am Flora C. Alvarez from the Office of the City Agriculture, and this morning I stand before you to explain about the Implementing Rules and Regulation or R.A. 100068, also known as the Organic Agriculture Act of 2010.

Chair: You have no idea?

SP Chairperson: Thank you very much, City Agriculturist.

SP Chairperson: Thank you, City Agriculturist.

SP Chairperson: xxx To our fellow city councilors, SP Member 1 is recognized.

SP Member 1: Thank you, Honorable SP Chairperson. xxx

SP Chairperson: Thank you SP Member 1, SP Member 2 is now recognized.

SP Chairperson: Thank you, City Agriculturist. Let us now listen to Resource Person 4. Sir, please state your name and designation.

SP Chairperson: Thank you very much, City Budget Officer. SP Member 2 is recognized.

SP Chairperson: xxx I have given you copies, and my fellow councilors have been provided copies as well.

The codes such as 'legislative clarification,' 'procedural formalities in council meetings,' and 'distribution of materials' are indicative of the structured process in which legislative bodies operate. 'Legislative clarification' refers to the explanation and elucidation of laws, which in this case is the Organic Agriculture Act. 'Procedural formalities in council meetings' denote the established procedures that govern the conduct of the meetings, ensuring order and systematic discussion, which is evident from the recognition of various council members and the orderly transition between speakers. Lastly, 'distribution of materials' likely pertains to the dissemination of information or documents relevant to the legislation being discussed, which is a crucial step in the legislative process to inform and educate the council members about the matter at hand.

3.3. Program Execution and Support

3.3.1. outreach and engagement

SP Member 2: xxx I'm acknowledging our becoming City Agriculturist to reach out to the barangay officials to consider this, as it is a very good program.

xxx

The code, 'outreach and engagement,' is evident in SP Member 2's acknowledgment of the role of the City Agriculturist in reaching out to local officials, emphasizing the importance of grassroots involvement in agricultural programs.

3.3.2. operational flexibility

SP Member 2: Okay, if I may continue, even if it's not in the AIP, the submissions by OCVAS can still be executed, though I think not.

The code, 'operational flexibility in program execution,' reflects the adaptability required in implementing agricultural initiatives, as discussed by SP Member 2 regarding the execution of submissions by OCVAS outside the Annual Investment Plan (AIP).

3.3.3. AIP entry and project flexibility

City Budget Officer: xxx However, if we have leeway in the AIP, it's the AIP that will be entered, not our long-term projects, which can be implemented one by one, anytime.

The City Budget Officer's statement contributes to the code, 'AIP entry and project flexibility,' suggesting that while the AIP is a guiding document, and there is room for flexibility to accommodate long-term projects.

3.3.4. optimism for implementation

SP Chairperson: "Thank you, SP Member 2, that's true, if you talk there will be no problem for us, we can implement it, thank you."

The code, 'optimism for implementation,' is captured by the SP Chairperson's positive response to SP Member 2, indicating a willingness and readiness to implement agricultural plans.

3.3.5. Department of Agriculture support

Resource Person 1: xxx the Department of Agriculture has built a small building on my farm where these concoctions are made, such as FFJ and amino phases. They also constructed a facility for producing wood vinegar, xxx

The code 'Department of Agriculture support,' is directly referenced by Resource Person 1's mention of the department's construction of facilities on his farm, which signifies institutional backing for agricultural innovation.

3.3.6. resources for organic farming

Resource Person 1: xxx So, perhaps we can be helped to be provided with organic seeds so we will no longer use the ones we buy from... xxx

'Resources for organic farming,' the seventh code, is derived from Resource Person 1's call for assistance in obtaining organic seeds, highlighting the need for resources that support sustainable practices.

3.4. Legislative Clarity and Framework

3.4.1. clarity in legislation

SP Member 3: xxx there might be a misinterpretation that the technical committee and the council mentioned are different, that's it. And Madam SP Chairperson, regarding the functions provision, no.7, it is written here, the committee shall have the following functions, so we know the difference between shall and may, shall is stronger and since this is an ordinance it needs to be absolute and not negotiable.

The code, 'clarity in legislation,' is drawn from the emphasis on the definitive language used in ordinances, as indicated by SP Member 3's concern over the use of 'shall' instead of 'may.' This underscores the necessity for absolute terms in legal documents to avoid misinterpretation and ensure enforceability.

3.4.2. institutional mechanism amendments

SP Chairperson: xxx I just have a correction here, Ma'am Flor, in Article 2, Institutional Mechanism, Letter B, and Composition.

The code, 'institutional mechanism amendments,' relates to the SP Chairperson's correction regarding the composition of institutional mechanisms, suggesting a need for ongoing refinement of the structures that support policy implementation.

3.4.3. policy provisions for organic farming

SP Member 2: xxx Section 336 states that the budget is only for that purpose.

Similarly, the code, 'policy provisions for organic farming,' is inferred from SP Member 2's reference to budget allocations, which implies that financial resources are earmarked specifically for organic farming initiatives, reflecting targeted policy support.

3.4.4. governmental support

City Agriculturist: The city government will pay.

Governmental support is evident in City Agriculturist's statements, indicating that the city government will finance certain activities and that there is a higher-level endorsement from national boards. This demonstrates the layered support structure from local to national levels.

3.4.5. institutional framework

City Agriculturist: It comes from the national board, as there are certifying bodies.

The code, 'institutional framework,' is derived from the acknowledgment of certifying bodies, which are integral to the validation and standardization processes within the agricultural sector.

3.4.6. procedural clarity

SP Member 1: So, you will endorse the product to the national level, and then they will determine if it's organic, they will issue the certificate and also collect the payment, how much do you think that would be?

Procedural clarity is highlighted by SP Member 1's inquiry into the endorsement and certification process for organic products, which points to the need for transparent procedures that stakeholders can easily understand and navigate.

3.4.7. inclusion of industrial development councils

City Budget Officer: xxx In my opinion, it seems the IDC is not included in the ordinance for people to appreciate the importance of organic produce.

The 'inclusion of the industrial development council' in the ordinance suggests a multidisciplinary approach to policy-making, where various stakeholders, including those from industrial sectors, are involved in the legislative process.

3.5. Organic Farming Legislation and Aspirations

3.5.1. importance of ordinances for farmers

Resource Person 4: xxx I can say that this is significant for our fellow farmers, who we know regard farming as a livelihood and business. Xxx

The code 'importance of ordinance for farmers,' is drawn from Resource Person 4's statement, emphasizing the significance of the ordinance for farmers who view farming as both a livelihood and a business. This underscores the ordinance's potential to provide a structured and supportive environment for farmers to thrive in organic farming.

3.5.2. challenges without a legal framework

Resource Person 4: xxx I believe that if this does not become an ordinance, it will be challenging to implement. We have no problem; we understand, but explaining this to our fellow farmers might be difficult. Therefore, it is excellent that this will now become an ordinance. xxx

This code, challenges without legal framework, reflects the predicament local farmers might have if the city will not enact an organic agricultural ordinance. Widespread adoption is viewed to be impossible if a binding and in effect ordinance lacks. Promoting organic agriculture practices will not be compulsory in the city with the absence of a legal

framework. Since the law punishes only what it provides, achieving a city-wide organic farming compliance is impossible.

3.5.3. gratitude for enactment

Resource Person 4: xxx I am grateful because today, an ordinance on organic farming will be enacted.

xxx

With the words expressed by the resource person, the code gratitude for enactment was generated. The statement further reflect the appreciation of the resource person on the formal recognition and legal action taken by the city government in terms of formulating and along the way, enacting, of an organic agriculture ordinance. From this, it can be assumed that a positive reception from the stakeholders can also lead to a strong support and promotion of a sustainable and innovative agriculture practice in the city.

3.5.4. legislative aspirations and organic food accessibility

SP Chairperson: xxx We really want this matter to become an ordinance so that what we are discussing here can be experienced, that our food will be organic.

xxx

The desire of enacting an organic agriculture ordinance as it will lead to better access in organic produce as expressed by the Chairperson is embodied in the code legislative aspirations and organic food accessibility. Since vagueness still exist in the

classification of a -produce as to organic, hybrid, or inorganic due to lacking standards of certification, the local legislators views the formulation or org aid agricultural ordinance as an instrument that will facilitate or start the accessibility of the locals to certified organic food. Though certified organic -produce are available in the key supermarkets of the city, still, an organic crop locally produced by the city is far from reality, until, a certification process will eventually push through.

In summary, the theme Integration of R&D in Formulation Agricultural Ordinance is composed of the following sub-themes: (1) organizational dynamics and support system; (2) legislative processes and material distribution; (3) program execution and support; (4) legislative clarity and framework; and (5) organic farming legislation and aspirations.

In order to answer the main research question posted for the study, ethnomethodological approach was employed by the researcher. This involved a detailed examination of the interactions and communications among stakeholders during committee hearings. By scrutinizing the statements made, as reflected from the documented information Journal of Proceedings, the research revealed how different types of knowledge and the language patterns and communication generated contribute to the shaping of agricultural ordinances.

The presented forms of knowledge plays an essential and crucial role in the formulation of an organic agriculture ordinance. The subtle references to R&D made by the stakeholders, as embodied in the identified language patterns and communications, are empirical evidences that inform and influence policy formulation. The knowledge, language patterns, and communications embodied by the stakeholders: the local smallholder farmers, members of farmer-related associations, local agriculturist, city

government head employees, and local legislators; were source of practical understanding that contributed to the formulation of a more applicable, effective, and suited to the current needs of the research locale. The lived experiences of the stakeholders, as reflected in the forms of knowledge, language patterns, and communication the uniquely possess are vital elements in the legislative process of policy formulation.

Integration Model: R&D in the Legislative Process

The researcher proposes a model for the integration of R&D in the legislative process of ordinance formulation of a city government, as follows:

Figure 1. *Integrating R&D in the Legislative Process of Ordinance Formulation.*

Three pivotal elements were identified by the researcher: (1) Role of R&D, (2) Legislative Mandate, and (3) Public Policy Legislation.

The Role of R&D. The Role of R&D bears essential connection with Legislative Mandate. The connection it has with previous promotes knowledge flow as it leads to an evidenced-based policy making. With the empirical data and scientific evidences provided by R&D, public policies are drafted, debated, and refined as ordinances that are grounded in the actual reality responsive to the needs of the society, at the same time, an effective resolve in addressing issues. The resource persons involved in the conduct of committee hearing for the formulation of an organic agriculture ordinance in the locale of the study are local experts whom the local legislators consult with. With the presence of these various experts in agriculture, local legislators are able to see the wide perspective of the possible impacts and enacted ordinance can bring in the community. With the presence of R&D and its connection to the legislative mandate of enacting ordinances, the legislative department of a city government promotes a synergistic collaboration that is vital to the process of crafting more comprehensive and effective public policies.

Public Policy Legislation. The Role of R&D and its connection to Public Policy Legislation facilitates stakeholder engagement. This side of connection draws the line of addressing emerging issues in the locale. The new challenges posted by issues of climate change, environmental sustainability, and agricultural innovation can be addressed by R&D. As local legislators gain foresight and awareness on these issues, they also perform proactive actions by way of responsive policies that aims to mitigate risks and leverage opportunities. The complementing connection of the Role of R&D and Public Policy Legislation provides for an evaluative role. Grounded in R&D evidences,

policy formulation undergoes assessment to identify what works, what does not work, and what needs to be adjusted. Thus, a policy undergoing rigorous process of formulation and enactment that is more dynamic and more responsive.

Legislative Mandate. Legislative Mandate and Public Policy Legislation are connected as they play essential role in facilitating policy formulation in a city government. The development and adoption of an organic agriculture ordinance in a city government is promoted and encouraged by the performance of the legislative mandate of a city government. Along with this, local legislation facilitates coordination as policy formulation gathers various stakeholders: in the case of the study, coordination among several city government offices, smallholder farmers, and farming associations. Priorities are also set as Legislative Mandate often outlines specific goals, and targets. Addressing these aids policymakers in ensuring resources are allocated and obligated to significant pressing matters. The connection is also vital in establishing policy formulation framework that includes clear definition of scopes, objectives, policy declaration, salient features, penal provisions, institutional mechanism and implementing rules and regulations, and supplemental provisions, or the embodiment of a detailed local ordinance.

Chapter VI

RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study “Surfacing R&D in the legislative process: an ethnomethodological analysis of the journal of proceedings of a city government’s committee hearing on an agricultural ordinance” is a graduate thesis that explores on the process how R&D evidences in terms of forms of knowledge and language patterns and communication are integrated in the legislative process of policy formulation in a city government with the use of ethnomethodological approach as both research method and research framework.

Summary

The methodology and framework popularized by Harold Garfinkel was instrumental in proving the integration of R&D in the process of policy formulation. Ethnomethodology focuses on the discovery, analysis, and interpretation of the everyday practices and interactions embodied by the relevant stakeholders involved during the conduct of a committee hearing by the city government’s legislative department.

With the qualitative approach, the practical reasoning, actions, and interactions of both local legislators and stakeholders proves that R&D evidences and data are integrated in the formulation of an organic agriculture ordinance, as backed up with the displayed forms of knowledge and language patterns and communication generated from the documented information analysed by the researcher. Underpinnings relevant to ethnomethodology in form of detailed observations derived from the iterative scanning

and analysing committee hearing and public consultation are proven to influence the process of policy formulation as a subtle standard or framework element.

This approach also identifies how R&D findings are understood, valued, and utilized by local policymakers, uncovering informal negotiations and compromises in the mandate of conducting legislative process. Ethnomethodological techniques, such as detailed observations and analyses of council meetings, document the procedural and interactional subtleties influencing policy formulation, demonstrating how R&D is a socially negotiated element within the legislative framework.

The study aims to answer the following research questions:

Main Research Question:

1. How is R&D currently integrated into the process of formulating agricultural ordinances in a city government's legislative department?

Specific Research Questions:

1. What role does knowledge play in shaping agricultural ordinances, even when R&D is not explicitly mentioned?
2. How do language patterns and communication within a city government's legislative department reflect R&D-related discussions?

The research focused on the exploration towards the role of R&D in legislative processes, further discovering how it is integrated into the formulation of agricultural ordinances, the influence of forms of knowledge, and the reflection of R&D in language

and communication patterns. It reveals the indirect presence of R&D, the impact of form of knowledge on ordinance development, and how language patterns and communication within a city government's legislative department conveys R&D concepts, influencing legislative outcomes.

This chapter employs an ethnomethodological approach to explore the integration of R&D within local policy formulation. It analyzes the Journal of Proceedings of Conducted Committee Hearing spearheaded by the legislative department of a city government, detailing the formulation of an ordinance. The research locale is vividly described, and methodical procedures for data collection and analysis are outlined. The research locale's legislative dynamics was further understood as codes, sub-themes, and themes were generated.

The researcher postulates the following findings:

1. Integration of R&D in Formulating Agricultural Ordinances: The formulation of local policy relied on existing research and data from external sources. The process lacks of dedicated R&D initiatives within the legislative department of the city government. R&D-related discussions are embedded in the everyday interactions and decision-making processes of the council. The analysis highlights the importance of social dynamics, power relations, and cultural norms in shaping how R&D is perceived and utilized in legislative processes.
2. Forms of Knowledge: Knowledge, derived from the experiences and expertise of council members and local stakeholders, presented and classified in various forms,

significantly influences the shaping of agricultural ordinances. This knowledge often fills gaps where formal R&D is absent, providing practical insights and context-specific solutions.

3. Language Patterns and Communication: Language patterns and communication within the legislative department reflect an implicit understanding of R&D concepts, even when not explicitly mentioned. Discussions often include references to empirical evidence, best practices, and anecdotal experiences of both local legislators and resource persons that align with R&D principles.

The integration of R&D in the formulation of local ordinances, particularly in the agricultural sector as initiated by the local legislators, can be subtly discerned through an ethnomethodological analysis of the local legislative proceedings. The qualitative study posits that while R&D is not explicitly or obviously referenced and cited, its influence is identified in the legislative process. This is evident in the language patterns and terminologies used, such as references to 'foliar organic fertilizers', 'ferment plant juice', 'fermented fruit juice', 'open-pollinated seeds', 'soil studies' and other research-inclined words which indicate a scientific approach to agriculture that is characteristic of R&D-driven initiatives.

Conclusion

R&D serves as the cornerstone of progressive policy formulation in agriculture, yet its integration into the legislative framework often remains an informal practice. This study highlights the critical role of R&D within the legislative department of a city government

and emphasizes the synergy between traditional knowledge and modern scientific methods and its inclusion in shaping public policies. It underscores the vitality of knowledge, though subtle, still reflects significant presence of R&D in legislative forms of knowledge and language patterns and communication, emphasized for a more structured approach to embedding R&D in the creation of agricultural policies. It also reflects on the implications of the findings as it offers a conclusive understanding of the role R&D plays in enhancing the formulation of an ordinance. Since R&D proves to enable a transformative potential if applied in or incorporated in the legislative framework, shaping policies that are both innovative and grounded in empirical research are achievable.

Thus, the researcher opines the following conclusive statements:

1. The presence of R&D is currently limited and informal in the place of the study, in terms of formulating agricultural ordinance in the legislative department of a city government. The integration of R&D in legislative processes lacks a formal structure. This suggests a potential underutilization of scientific insights in policy-making, which could be pivotal in addressing the multifaceted challenges of modern agriculture.
2. The presence and inclusion of R&D is essential in crafting agricultural policies. The interplay between the forms of knowledge, daily language patterns and communication is essential in enhancing public policy formulation. The organizational culture of a legislative department promotes a process that are both based on practices and proactive. The inclusion of R&D evidences and data enhances the quality and content of proposed ordinance. The process of integrating R&D in public policy formulation is an evident process of acculturation grounded in the unique

organizational culture of the locale and promotion of innovative and proactive solutions.

3. The study confirmed the various forms of knowledge displayed by the stakeholders that are indispensable in proving that R&D evidences and data are present and are being utilized in the process of public policy formulation. It is an essential component in the standardization of the existing framework of the locale.
4. The language patterns and communication are not explicitly acknowledged, but is frequently referenced as evidenced by the repeated use of R&D-related words in the analysed documented information. This indicates that, while not formally acknowledged, R&D's influence is present in the legislative dialogue in the process of shaping policies through an undercurrent of scientific thought.
5. The essential role of R&D offers a benchmark for evaluation and bridges the gap between scientific integration and policy formulation. It is not only an adjunct component to the legislative process but a driving force for progressive change and a standard set for measuring policy efficacy and completeness. The gap between scientific research and policy-making is bridged by R&D, ensuring that legislative outcomes are informed by the necessary, practical, and beneficial latest advancements and empirical evidence.
6. Ethnomethodological analysis provides significant insights to illuminate and establish the shared need of R&D and legislative processes, emphasizing the vitality of a more structured approach to incorporating R&D in policy-making. It is instrumental in

identifying and advocating for a more standardized approach to R&D integration, consequently leading to improved and informed decision-making and responsive policy outcomes. This analysis not only presents the current state of affairs but also points towards a future where R&D is an integral and formalized part of a city government's legislative process, leading to more dynamic and responsive governance not only in the field of agriculture, but to the entirety of sectors addressed by local legislation.

R&D is significant in the context and system of agriculture, particularly within the enactment of an Organic Agriculture Ordinance. The inclusion of R&D in the formulation process of an ordinance displays a deliberate move by the legislative body of promoting innovation and scientific inquiry as building blocks of agricultural progress. City ordinances, regarded as reference tool and representation of the general basis or benchmark of higher forms of policies and programs of the government, need to ensure that they are grounded on evidenced-based and research-based elements responsive to the evolving trends of the environment and changing technological developments.

With the intricate demands of agriculture of achieving sustainability and food security along with the impacts and challenges of climate change and environmental forces, R&D-based policy formulation stands as a transformative force in agricultural policy-making with its transcending and supplemental role. It is concluded that this study's findings highlights the progress achieved and the expansive potential for further advancements, especially in embedding R&D at the very genesis of policy formulation. Pivotal as it is, the integration of R&D in the process of formulating public policy ensures

that every enacted ordinances are scientific-based and at the same time reflects the socio-cultural fiber of the locale.

Recommendations

The researcher presents two aspects of recommendations: methodological and practical. The methodological impacts of R&D in the legislative process aim to improve the objectivity and depth of future formulations of public policies. On the other hand, the practical recommendations are presented to promote a new practice of policy formulation, a process that includes or integrates R&D.

Methodological Impacts of R&D in Legislative Processes

Integrating R&D evidences and data in legislative process of formulating public policy contributes to an enhanced process of making decisions. As R&D serves as a source of empirical data and evidences, it boosts possibilities of improving and enhancing the quality of decisions formalized by the legislative department of a city government. It also promotes formulation of policies that are grounded on formal research rather than assumptions. Transparency and accountability are also highlighted as R&D evidences and data are incorporated into the legislative process. The origins and rationale that serve as bases for legislative decisions as evidenced by detailed documentation and rigorous analysis promotes accountability. With the presence, inclusion, and utilization of R&D evidences and data, innovative approaches are discovered and applied in problem-solving related to the legislative process. New ideas can be tested and research-grounded policies are innovated and adopted. As stakeholders, composed of local experts, industry representatives, and public groups, engage in the process of local policy

formulation, involvement and active participation is achieved. In employing ethnomethodological approach, ethnomethodological insights are gained through the identification of daily practices, routines, and interactions within the conducted committee hearing. These are beneficial in producing legislative outcomes as it reveal implied rules and standards outlines legislative process. The integration of R&D evidences and data are precursors in assessing the impact and effectiveness of proposed ordinances. This creates an opportunity for enacting ordinances that are responsive to the needs of the community.

With the integration of R&D findings, the institutional framework of the legislative department promotes a legislative process that is grounded in expert opinions and current agricultural research findings. This also promotes an environment that is collaborative where local policymakers, local experts and researchers mutually work for the formulation of an informed and research-based ordinance. Coming up with an institutional framework of incorporating R&D in every proposed ordinance and discussion of the proposed policy by way of conducting committee hearing with invited experts leads to an effective mechanism of legislating local policies that are both responsive and abreast on the current trends in respective disciplines.

Embedding R&D in the legislative curriculum and framework bears an impact in the capacity and capability of the local legislators, as well as the legislative staff. Gaining this knowledge and skill empower those involved in the legislative process in the process of interpreting and utilizing R&D outputs purposively. This will result in the shaping of a new organizational culture of gaining adept skill in terms of analysing R&D outputs and incorporating them in drafting policies. Thus, an enhanced quality of public policy is created.

Practical Impacts of R&D in Legislative Processes

Integrating R&D in the legislative process lead to several transformative effects in the process of policy formulation. With established clear objectives grounded in R&D outputs, local policy formulation can be ensured that policy outputs are both scientific and responsive to the needs of the community. Be it in the field of agriculture or not, formulated policies are more targeted to be formed within the principles of sustainability and innovation.

R&D-based public policy can foster economic benefits and growth as new opportunities for development and investment are identified. In example, research findings that promotes innovative agricultural practices can boost economies as crop yields increase and crop production cost decrease due to R&D based local policy.

R&D-informed local policies are enablers of improved public health. In example, recent research findings on the use and effect of pesticides in local farming can push further formulation of policies in the banning and substituting of organic pesticides. This clearly protects both consumers and the environment on the negative effects of using traditional pesticides in local farming. This can further lead to the creation of both environmental and sustainable policies as backed up by research on soil health, water usage and consumption in agriculture, and sustainable practice in crop rotation depending on the weather seasons of the locale.

To further maximize the role of R&D and its integration in the legislative process of policy formulation in a city government, the following recommendations are presented:

1. Establishment of Establish Clear Strategic Objectives and Strategic Priorities. Define and include strategic objectives and strategic priorities stating the inclusion of R&D

data, evidences, and outputs in the formulation of local policies or city ordinances that are aligned with the local development agenda of the city.

2. **Strengthening of Organizational Frameworks and Process.** Standardized the process flow by incorporating the invitation of relevant local researchers, local scientists, and local experts in committee hearings and integrating current R&D evidences, data, and outputs in drafting local policies.
3. **Conducting of Trainings that Builds Capacity and Improves Skills.** The legislative department of the city government must design and implement capacity building activities for both local legislators and legislative staff that enable the fusing of R&D evidences, data, outputs, and findings in the legislative curriculum and in the process of drafting provisions and content of proposed ordinances.
4. **Implementing Systems for Monitoring and Evaluation Purposes.** Craft and implement mechanisms that promotes rigorous system of evaluating and monitoring the process of drafting, proposing, and enacting local ordinances. Monitoring and evaluation aids the identification and formulation of relevant strategies, areas that needs improvement, upholding of accountability in the process of legislation.

With the provided recommendations, the legislative department of a city government can create a responsive and proactive environment that integrates R&D data, evidences, outputs, and findings in the context of public policies.

REFERENCES

- Anandajayasekeram, Ponniah. (2011). THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL R&D WITHIN THE AGRICULTURAL INNOVATION SYSTEMS FRAMEWORK.
- Campbell DM, Redman S, Jorm L, Cooke M, Zwi AB, Rychetnik L. Increasing the use of evidence in health policy: practice and views of policy makers and researchers. *Aust New Zealand Health Policy*. 2009 Aug 24;6:21. doi: 10.1186/1743-8462-6-21. PMID: 19698186; PMCID: PMC2739528.
- Carsten Daugbjerg, Alan Swinbank, An introduction to the 'new' politics of agriculture and food, *Policy and Society*, Volume 31, Issue 4, November 2012, Pages 259–270, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polsoc.2012.10.002>
- Ellen, M.E., Lavis, J.N., Horowitz, E. et al. How is the use of research evidence in health policy perceived? A comparison between the reporting of researchers and policy-makers. *Health Res Policy Sys* 16, 64 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-018-0345-6>
- Elliott H, Popay J. How are policy makers using evidence? Models of research utilisation and local NHS policy making. *J Epidemiol Community Health*. 2000 Jun; 54(6):461-8. doi: 10.1136/jech.54.6.461. PMID: 10818123; PMCID: PMC1731692.
- Garfinkel, H. (1967). *Studies in Ethnomethodology*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Gilanie, Ghulam. (2022). Knowledge and its Types.
- Gutiérrez Cano, L. F., Zарtha Sossa, J. W., Orozco Mendoza, G. L., Suárez Guzmán, L. M., Agudelo Tapasco, D. A., & Quintero Saavedra, J. I. (2023). Agricultural innovation system: Analysis from the subsystems of R&D, training, extension, and sustainability. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2023.1176366>
- Kristiansen, P., Taji, A., & Reganold, J. P. (Eds.). (2006). *Organic agriculture: A global perspective*. CSIRO Publishing.
- Mitton C, Adair CE, McKenzie E, Patten SB, Waye Perry B. Knowledge transfer and exchange: review and synthesis of the literature. *Milbank Q*. 2007 Dec; 85(4):729-68. doi: 10.1111/j.1468-0009.2007.00506.x. PMID: 18070335; PMCID: PMC2690353.
- Onwujekwe, O., Uguru, N., Russo, G. et al. Role and use of evidence in policymaking: an analysis of case studies from the health sector in Nigeria. *Health Res Policy Sys* 13, 46 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-015-0049-0>

- Orton L, Lloyd-Williams F, Taylor-Robinson D, O'Flaherty M, Capewell S. The use of research evidence in public health decision making processes: systematic review. *PLoS One*. 2011; 6(7):e21704. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0021704. Epub 2011 Jul 26. PMID: 21818262; PMCID: PMC3144216.
- Oxman, A.D., Vandvik, P.O., Lavis, J. N. et al. SUPPORT Tools for evidence-informed health Policymaking (STP) 2: Improving how your organisation supports the use of research evidence to inform policymaking. *Health Res Policy Sys* 7 (Suppl 1), S2 (2009). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1478-4505-7-S1-S2>
- Pal, Suresh. (2008). Agricultural R&D Policy and Institutional Reforms: Learning from the Experiences of India and China. *Economic and Political Weekly*. 43. 10.2307/40278912.
- Pierrette, Coulibaly & Du, Jian-guo & Diakit, Daniel. (2021). Sustainable agricultural practices adoption. *Agriculture (Pol'nohospodrstvo)*. 67. 166-176. 10.2478/agri-2021-0015.
- Stoian, M., Ion, R. A., Turcea, V. C., Nica, I. C., & Zemeleaga, C. G. (2022). The influence of governmental agricultural R&D expenditure on farmers' income—Disparities between EU member states. *Sustainability*, 14(17), 10596. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141710596>
- Tariq, Saira & Zakir, Rubeena. (2023). Evidence – Informed Policy Formulation and Implementation: A case study of 'Clean Air Policy' in Punjab, Pakistan. *Annals of King Edward Medical University*. 23. 392-399. 10.21649/akemu.v23i4.5518.

APPENDICES

APPENDICES

LIST OF TABLE

Table 1. Themes, Sub-themes, and Codes Generated

Table 2. Type of Knowledge Classification from Generated Codes

Table 3. Source of Statement of Generated Codes

LIST OF FIGURE

Figure 1. Integration of R&D in the Legislative Process of Formulating Agricultural Ordinance

TRANSCRIPT

Journal of Committee Hearing of Committee on Agriculture and Cooperatives, Held at Sangguniang Panlungsod Session Hall, on November 24, 2023 at 10:10 am

TRANSCRIPT

**Letterhead
Letterhead
Letterhead**

**JOURNAL OF COMMITTEE HEARING OF COMMITTEE ON AGRICULTURE AND
COOPERATIVES, HELD AT SANGGUNIANG PANLUNGSOD SESSION HALL,
ON NOVEMBER 24, 2023 AT 10:10 AM**

SUBJECT: AN ORDINANCE INSTITUTIONALIZING, PROMOTING AND
DEVELOPING ORGANIC AGRICULTURE IN THE CITY OF
BATANGAS PROVIDING FUNDS THEREFORE AND FOR OTHER
PURPOSES

CHAIRMAN: SP MEMBER ISIDRA ATIENZA

MEMBER: SP MEMBER NELSON CHAVEZ
SP MEMBER ZESTER CARLO HERNANDEZ
SP MEMBER MICHAEL VILLENA

SP MEMBERS: SP MEMBER KARLOS EMMANJUEL BUTED
SP MEMBER NESTOR DIMACUHA
SP MEMBER LORENZO GAMBOA, JR.
SK FEDERATION PRESIDENT MARCUS MANUEL CASTILLO

GUEST: SEE ATTACHMENT

X-----X

The meeting was formally initiated by the Honorable Councilor Isidra Atienza as the Chairperson of the Committee.

Chair: The Committee Hearing on Agriculture is now called to order. Good morning to everyone, to our fellow councilors present here, Councilor Michael Villena, Zester Hernandez, Junjun Gamboa, Karlos Buted, to my partner in service Councilor Boy Dimacuha, and to our SK Federation President, Hon. Marcus Castillo. Before we start, I would like to recognize the guests who are here, of course, our Mrs. Flora Alvarez,

OIC City Agriculturist, Mr. Victor Malibiran, President of the Batangas City Vegetable Growers Association, Mr. Emmanuel Zalada, President of the Batangas City Organic Farmers Association, Mr. Nilo Aclan, Vice President of the Batangas City Cacao Growers Association, and Ma'am Marissa Silva from the Banana Growers Association. Good morning to all of us. We are here because of an ordinance that we need to pass, the Organic Agriculture Ordinance. I just want to remind everyone before we start, we have rules, anyone who has a concern or question shall be recognized first by the chairperson, please state your name, your office, and designation first for record purposes. All questions must be addressed to the chairperson, so that we can proceed more efficiently. I have given you copies, and my fellow councilors have been provided copies as well.

I just have a brief background to share: the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) and the Department of Agriculture (DA) strongly encourage all Local Government Units (LGUs) to implement

R.A. 10068, also known as the Organic Agriculture Act of 2010. On May 31, 2018, the DILG and DA issued a Revised Joint Memorandum Circular that prescribes the rules and responsibilities of LGUs in the development, promotion, and implementation of the National Organic Agriculture Program as mandated by the law. Over the years, our city government has implemented numerous agricultural programs, witnessing our city's high aspirations to further enhance and keep up with the challenges of the times in agricultural matters. This year, separate offices for City Agriculture and City Veterinary were established. Therefore, I, your humble servant, along with my fellow councilors and members of the ordinance, have authored an ordinance titled, 'An Ordinance Institutionalizing, Promoting and Developing Organic Agriculture in the City of Batangas, Providing Funds Therefore and for Other Purposes.' As I mentioned earlier that we each have a copy, I would like to hear from Ms. Flora Alvarez, the OIC of the City Agriculturist, regarding your comments or suggestions on the draft of the Proposed Ordinance that I provided to you.

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: Good morning, Madam Chair and to your fellow councilors this morning. I am Flora C. Alvarez from the Office of the City Agriculture, and this morning I stand before you to explain about the Implementing Rules and Regulation or R.A. 10068, also known as the Organic Agriculture Act of 2010. I am pleased because through you, this ordinance will now be clarified. The truth is, our office advocates for the implementation of organic farming here in the City of Batangas. Why? Because we know that our environment is already devastated, we already have problems when it comes to the environment, land pollution, air pollution, and water pollution. When we say organic, it means farming that is free from chemicals, we will not use inorganic fertilizers, pesticides, and pharmaceuticals. So, what we will use are natural resources, organic fertilizers from plant and animal waste, which pose minimal risk to the environment, can produce healthy and nutritious fruits and vegetables, thus greatly benefiting human health, avoiding the destruction of natural habitats or natural resources. The use of chemicals causes the destruction of the ecology or biodiversity of our environment. Therefore, this ordinance will be a great help if implemented here in our City of Batangas, it will also help farmers to be safe from the harmful effects of chemicals and then provide additional income for the farmers. Why? Because selling fruits and vegetables that are organically grown is more expensive than those grown with chemicals, and moreover, they can help in restoring the beautiful and lush environment in our city, thank you.

Chair: Thank you very much, Mrs. Flora Alvarez. That's why when we talked about the need to have an ordinance on organic farming, your servant indeed did research, I spoke with my fellow councilors if they could join us in passing this organic agriculture, right? When we talked about passing our organic farming, what you said was very beautiful even if you explained it in a short time. If this is approved, how much do you think will be our budget here, appropriation allocation?

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: The budget is already integrated into our ... that we use, what we just need to focus on are the certifications needed. It is necessary because for them to be called organic products or organically grown vegetables and fruits, there must be certifying bodies that will certify that they are organically grown. So, it requires a large fee before we can be accredited, registered, or given certification as certified organically grown products.

Chair: You have no idea?

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: What I hear is that certification alone costs sixty thousand (60,000) for a single product, plus there are other fees because many studies need to be conducted. It takes several years before you can be granted certification because implementing organic farming takes five (5) years before you can be certified as organic practitioners. There are studies concerning the soil, the crops to be planted, soil amendments with organic fertilizer, and there is a certain time required to be granted certification for it to be certified as an organic product.

Chair: Thank you, Mrs. Flora. From what I've heard from you, I believe our city government can handle this, which is probably why Mr. Perlada left after speaking with you, as he must have been satisfied as well. To our fellow city councilors, Councilor Junjun Gamboa is recognized.

SP Member L. Gamboa, Jr.: Thank you, Honorable Chair. I noticed in the ordinance that there is an organic farming test, but do we have identified locations and a mechanism to protect the said farming test?

Chair: Who will answer, Mrs. Flora Alvarez?

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: Currently, sir, since 2000 we have implemented farming, but we cannot say it is totally organically grown because they use hybrid seeds and organic fertilizers, including organic foliar fertilizer. However, the seeds they use are not endemic, they are not hybrid, and my colleague here at the front says the bananas are totally organic, but that's an assumption because they are not yet certified. They do not use chemical fertilizers, they are organic, but we cannot say they are organic because there are no certifying bodies to certify them.

SP Member L. Gamboa, Jr.: Madam Chair, let me repeat because I noticed in Section 9, as I first opened it, it mentions the Organic Farming Test, which is why I asked if we have identified locations where we can place our organic farms. Do you know of any locations where we can conduct an organic farming test?

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: We have some in Soro-soro Ibaba, Tabangao, and Tulo. SP Member L. Gamboa, Jr.: So, three locations?

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: Yes.

SP Member L. Gamboa, Jr.: Okay, yesterday I noticed, we went to OCVAS, and I asked Madam Chair because when we were about to leave, she told me that those are organic. Because I saw that what was being watered seemed like the water was mixed with something like cream. So, I just want to ask what is being watered on the plants.

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: What we have at OCVAS farming is organically grown, we just don't claim it unless certified. Those are plant juices, the FFJ, Fermented Fruit Juice, and FPJ, Fermented Plant Juice, those are fermented plants and that's what we use for watering.

SP Member L. Gamboa, Jr.: That's what is being watered? Mrs. Flora Alvarez: Yes.

SP Member L. Gamboa, Jr.: Thank you, thank you Madam Chair.

Chair: Thank you, Councilor Junjun, Councilor Boy Dimacuha is now recognized.

SP Member N. Dimacuha: Thank you, Madam Chair, good morning to everyone. Section 6 of the Proposed Ordinance pertains to the participation of all barangays. The barangay is encouraged to initiate its own short, medium, and long-term programs with a specific budget allocation from its Internal Revenue Allotment for organic agriculture. Although the law encourages barangay participation, I believe that not all barangays that have prepared their budgets are aware of this because we are now in the process of preparing the annual barangay budget. Therefore, if they are to participate, I believe it is not yet included in their Annual Barangay Council Investment Plan, so we cannot just rely on the barangay because, as I mentioned, their budget was prepared prior to the proposed ordinance enactment. It is beneficial that a member of the council is from the league of barangays, and perhaps ABC President Dondon Dimacuha could inform all 105 barangays to allocate a certain amount for the realization of this program. This is what I foresee as a potential problem that we are actually already facing because we do not have the funds that should also be provided by the barangay program. I think one of the issues is the early submission of our barangay budget, which did not consider Section 6, the participation of all barangays in allocating a budget from their IRA. When it comes to the IRA, which is 20%, it is always allocated to infrastructure development, and it is rare for such programs to be included, especially those related to gardening. The content is good, and I agree with it. However, we are somewhat lacking in time because if this will have an allocation, it might be included in the supplemental budget as well. I'm acknowledging our becoming City Agriculturist to reach out to the barangay officials to consider this, as it is a very good program. It also aims to protect the environment, which is a current topic of discussion. The use of fertilizers, which contain chemical compositions, cannot be said to be safe, although there are certain limits on how to use them. But over time, with the amount they apply or use, it seems to exceed the limit. For example, currently, it's only half, then you add again, it becomes one whole, add again, and it becomes one and a half. So, we should also know and study what and lastly, the funding for Mr. Perlada, Article 5 of the proposed ordinance Section 26, and the funding requirements. The draft ordinance may cost one million (1,000,000) initially, just the initial amount of 1,000,000 for the implementation of this ordinance subject to the annual allocation of such amount as may be deemed necessary. Do we have in our Annual Investment Plan (AIP) a project that will support this ordinance? It's only 1 million, is this program in our AIP when it comes to...

Mr. Manolo M. Perlada: I am not certain about the AIP, which is why I returned because as I said earlier, my answer would remain the same. However, as I was walking, I was thinking. This is a program of the City Agriculture, and their funds are lump-summed for different purposes, their MOOE and all, and there is nothing specified there for the implementation of an organic agriculture program. So, it is possible to allocate funds from the appropriation because, for example, if we base it on the ordinance, we really would set aside funds like for the Batangas City Health Program, where we have one hundred million, so we have to have another program under, maybe under the... of the city mayor with a 1 million appropriation fund... But for instance, if OCVAS also implements it as part of their program, it will become part of their annual appropriation and will no longer be specific for this purpose, it would be like it's over and above the appropriation of OCVAS.

SP Member N. Dimacuha: "Okay, if I may continue, even if it's not in the AIP, the submissions by OCVAS can still be executed, though I think not."

Mr. Manolo M. Perlada: "The program to be implemented by OCVAS is not specified in the AIP like other programs. There might be something, let's say under programs to be implemented by agriculture, I'm not so sure, I haven't actually read it, but I can clarify that. However, if we have leeway in the AIP, it's the AIP that will be entered, not our long-term projects, which can be implemented one by one, anytime."

SP Member N. Dimacuha: "Okay, lastly Madam Chair, it's very clear under RA 7160, Section 336 what the allocation is exclusively for the purpose. Now, the question is, this is about the implementation, the purpose ordinance of organic farming, so if we don't have funds for this, it won't materialize because it's very clear, government funds will be exclusively used for the purpose. So, we need to identify if this is included in the OCVAS program because if it's not included, we will be very saddened, it won't proceed unless you have communication with our good City Budget Officer and discuss it thoroughly. We know our budget officer is kind, as long as we ask, it's given, we keep asking but it's not given. So, that's the way to help us realize this. So, you're hoping that our good officer will help you out for the realization of this program, Madam Chair, thank you."

Chair: "Thank you, Councilor Boy, that's true, if you talk there will be no problem for us, we can implement it, thank you."

Mr. Manolo M. Perlada: Councilor Boy is correct, if the ordinance already includes a funding requirement for an initial fund, it will indeed be allocated there. That's why I mentioned earlier that it is over and above the appropriation for OCVAS. They cannot use it for any other exclusive purpose. That's why I was saying earlier that if we could integrate it into the programs solely implemented by OCVAS, they could do so upon the execution of the 2024 budget. Because when there are such requirements in the law specifying funding, we will indeed allocate it with its own line, which we call line budgeting, and they cannot use it for any other purpose. Now, they should also clarify in the process what is needed, what will be purchased, what should be paid for, so we can also correct whether it's MOOE, capital outlays, or whatever we need. Because the 1 million mentioned here in our proposed ordinance is very generic, I think OCVAS, the Office of Agriculture, can answer that, it's confusing because it's the Office of the City Agriculturist that will implement these things.

Chair: Thank you, Mr. Manolo Perlada. Now let's hear from our OIC City Agriculturist, Mrs. Flora Alvarez.

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: Yes, our City Budget Officer is indeed kind. Actually, part of the organic agriculture is already being implemented by city agriculture, and we have ... when it comes to soil amendments and foliar organic fertilizers. So, what the city budget mentioned, by next year we will just identify what is needed for the implementation of organic agriculture.

Chair: Thank you, ma'am Flora Alvarez. Let us now listen to Mr. Victor Malibiran. Sir, please state your name and designation.

Mr. Victor Malibiran: Thank you very much, Madam Chair. I am Victor Malibiran from Batangas City. I am grateful because today, an ordinance on organic farming will be enacted. I can say that this is significant for our fellow farmers, who we know regard farming as a livelihood and business. I believe that if this does not become an ordinance, it will be challenging to implement. We have no problem; we understand, but explaining this to our fellow farmers might be difficult. Therefore, it is excellent that this will now become an ordinance. Thank you very much.

Chair: Thank you very much, Mr. Malibiran. Let us now invite the President of the Organic Farmers Association, Mr. Emmanuel Zalada, to speak.

Mr. Emmanuel Zalada: Good morning Madam Chair, good morning to my fellow councilors. I am Emmanuel Zalada, the President of the Batangas City Organic Farmers Association. From my perspective on organic, because I have been trying organic farming for several years now, I am also using concoctions that I make on my farm. I also have composting facilities; the Department of Agriculture has built a small building on my farm where these concoctions are made, such as FFJ and amino phases. They also constructed a facility for producing wood vinegar, which is the process of extracting liquid from fresh wood. This wood is burned in a chamber, and the resulting liquid is the wood vinegar. I am already using these methods. This wood vinegar, obtained from burning fresh wood that passes through a chamber with water inside, can be used as a spray for plants. So, what I did before with a drum of water, that's the foliar that serves as a bloom booster fertilizer for the plants. In the composting facility, that's what I use for quick decomposition when I water it on my accumulated grass or remaining waste in the field, the wood vinegar decomposes quickly, and it has many uses. So now, in my planting of plants, vegetables, I am also using organic methods. What I really didn't fully understand at first was that the seeds I was using were not really organic but were hybrids. So, it turns out that the seeds used should be organic seeds. So, that is if it comes from organic seeds, I do not know how the organic seeds will be supplied to us. So, perhaps we can be helped to be provided with organic seeds so we will no longer use the ones we buy from ..., that's all, thank you.

Chair: Thank you, Mr. Zalada, what we have heard is very educational for us, we have only heard about it now, and here in, Mr. Manolo Perlada is recognized.

Mr. Manolo M. Perlada: Mr. Zalada, what you said was beautiful, perhaps there is another way like in the fields when the first harvest of corn is aged and then placed behind the granary to be sun-dried, which is what is used for planting, not the seeds bought from the market. Perhaps that is the process that our City Agriculture should study so that we do not always buy new, we have only now heard that the seeds we

are buying are hybrid and not organic. So, if we are really going to promote organic farming, it would be better, ma'am Flor, to study how to initially obtain organic seeds and then after that, to have a process on how we will preserve seeds from our harvests. Because I think that is the right process since I grew up on our island where those seeds were really hung behind the granary, and every rainy season, that is what will be sorted by the mothers and then planted again in the fields. So, again, it will just cycle, getting a new harvest and even Mung beans or whatever type of plant, which is my recommendation.

Chair: Thank you very much, Mr. Manolo Perlada. Councilor Boy is recognized.

SP Member N. Dimacuha: Thank you, Madam Chair. That's correct, under RA 7627, you have the right to attend proper planning and study what's present. For example, Mr. Emmanuel mentioned corn; when the seed was first planted, it was organic, so the first harvest was all organic. The problem now is we don't know if what we're planting is organic because we haven't seen any of the crops certified as organic. At OCVAS, all the seeds we distribute, are you certain that those are organic?

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: The seeds we distribute are not organic but open-pollinated. When we say open-pollinated, it means that when it bears fruit, you can take seeds from it that will yield the same as the previous crop. The hybrid ones cannot be used for seeds because they are given for production purposes. The large areas that are planted need to produce a lot. The open-pollinated ones are for backyard gardening.

SP Member N. Dimacuha: How about the yellow corn, is it organic?

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: No, it's not organic because it's a yellow corn hybrid, and there's a certain metric ton target for production.

SP Member N. Dimacuha: Okay, last question, Madam Chair, if I may. Chair: Continue.

SP Member N. Dimacuha: When will it be possible, can you be certain as to when we can produce or provide organic seeds to farmers?

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: We need to establish an endemic farm, yes, so that we can produce organic seeds. SP Member N. Dimacuha: Who will initiate this?

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: The office will.

SP Member N. Dimacuha: The OCVAS.

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: Yes, we will establish a farm that will truly plant organic crops, from which we will obtain the seeds, certified organic seeds.

SP Member N. Dimacuha: So, how long do you think it will take to establish this? Mrs. Flora Alvarez: Three years, sir, because there is a certain time...

SP Member N. Dimacuha: Perhaps our friends here can help us with this, and it's not just one person involved; they have other colleagues as well. So, maybe as soon as possible we should educate them, teach them the correct process so we can get started. Because if we wait for the right time, I might not get to taste organic food anymore. But we should start as soon as possible to realize and implement this, thank you.

Chair: Thank you, Councilor Boy. That's why, ma'am Flor, when we discussed this, we need an ordinance. We really want this matter to become an ordinance so that what we are discussing here can be experienced, that our food will be organic. Let's now listen to Mr. Nilo Aclan, please state your name and designation.

Mr. Nilo Aclan: Good morning Madam Chair Nilo Aclan, Vice President of the Batangas City Cacao Growers Association. You know, it is truly wonderful that we are providing a budget particularly for this project, but now we have so many organic farmers who actually do not know that they are organic farmers. One thing we can help with, as Councilor Boy said, is if we are still waiting for funding, but now we have many, particularly banana growers. We have an endemic variety of bananas, actually, most of the bananas produced in our barangays, especially those not in large quantities, are organic. They do not use fertilizer nor do pesticides on their crops, but our farmers not have the incentive to increase production because the price of our bananas is the same or even lower than what we see in the market, which are beautiful and produced by... So, if you think about it, our farmers' bananas coming from the fields are organic, but we do not notice and we do not buy them. So, the funding is very good, but now the support that the farmers are asking for is for us to let them know, and it is good that we have an annual celebration, The Organic Farmers Festival, where we can tell our barangays to bring their products there, of course, certification is needed. We can do this, here is our OCVAS always ready to help. This requires soil testing, monitoring, and it needs to be certified because we know there are no pesticides, no fertilizers, and it is endemic, but they cannot continue because there is no market, and if there is a market, it is not bought. What happens is it ends up as pig feed because the ones from Davao look better, but these are organic. So, that is the assistance requested by the farmers to make this known and to raise awareness about this matter. It would be beneficial for us to receive support in the fund for producing organic pesticides and fertilizers, but the ordinary farmers who already have crops will be more encouraged if they know that their products can compete in the market. That is what we are asking for, that we may be able to provide information to the majority, which is needed now. In fact, those who truly produce organic fruits are the wealthy because they have the capital, and they support each other even without this, they have support. However, our small farmers tend to lose heart in continuing to farm because we do not give them enough support, which is all from me, thank you very much.

Chair: Thank you very much, Mr. Aclan. Perhaps this is the beginning of our assistance to you, especially me, because as I always say, I am here, Councilor Momshie Ched Atienza, and we were able to study because of farming, so we are united in this. I also know that my fellow councilors will join me, what we just need here is information dissemination, right, to let everyone know. Let's now listen to Ms. Marissa Silva, ma'am you're recognized.

Ms. Narissa Silva: Thank you very much, good morning to all of you. I am Narissa Silva, the Secretary of the Banana Growers Association. Our President, Mr. Teddy Chavez, is currently away on business. Regarding our banana farming, as sir has explained, the needs of the farmers in banana cultivation have been discussed. Now, from my own experience, since I also cultivate bananas, there are various varieties of bananas. Sometimes, as sir mentioned, they are not easily sold because there are now varieties that are not very marketable. There are also bananas that are indeed of good quality. However, we encounter issues with some seedlings being too soft, even before they ripen, and once they do, they become too soft to be sold in the market.

This makes it challenging for us banana farmers to market our produce, sometimes resorting to feeding them to pigs or goats. This is sometimes the reality, leading to some banana farmers not achieving successful farming practices. Ma'am, regarding the tissue culture like the one at UP, it is available, but it seems not yet here... We have sometimes acquired it from UP. Tissue culture is done in a laboratory. It is also something we can study to supply to our farmers. Thank you very much, ma'am.

Chair: Thank you very much, but it is saddening to hear from you that our bananas are going to waste.

Ms. Narissa Silva: Because, ma'am, when the prices really drop, that's when, ma'am, sometimes the bananas are indeed very cheap.

Chair: Alright, thank you very much for your input. Any questions from our colleagues? Councilor Junjun is recognized.

SP Member L. Gamboa, Jr.: Good morning again, based on my observation in our meeting, there were mentions of both organic and non-organic, like the bananas, which are organic, such as the Lakatan variety. I see in our area, we simply apply chicken manure to the bananas and they fruit effortlessly. Thus, I can also say that the banana hearts we used to have were organic. However, Mr. Emmanuel mentioned that they have purchased F1 seeds, but the watering and fertilizing methods used should be organic. We should also consider how many cycles it takes to breed chickens until a pure breed is obtained. Therefore, we must study the process of seed regeneration because when these seeds bear fruit, we call it a 50/50 chance of having an organic tree and the F1 seeds. Now, when these are bred to achieve a 50/50 ratio, we aim to return the fruit to its organic state until we obtain a pure breed. Only then can we say that these seeds are almost entirely organic; that's just something I've noticed. But I hope we can also pinpoint our plants that are truly organic, like the banana heart, which I am certain is organic. We should also inform our citizens which ones are organic. The Lakatan bananas are very delicious, and if not sold, they are fed to pigs or given away, and that is what I consider truly organic, madam chair.

Chair: Thank you very much, Councilor Jun. I believe our hearing won't take much longer. I just have a correction here, Ma'am Flor, in Article 2, Institutional Mechanism, Letter B, and Composition. Let me just read it, the council shall be composed of the following: number 7, three (3) authorized representatives from a farmer group engaged in organic agriculture for the past 3 years. Who can we put here as the 3 authorized representatives? And number 8, three (3) authorized representatives from Non-government Organizations also engaged in organic agriculture for the past 3 years. Please take note of that, Ma'am, and then, any questions from our... Okay, Councilor Junjun is recognized.

SP Member L. Gamboa, Jr.: I hope we can promote organic farming in schools because I've noticed it's not included in the provision, Madam Chair. Let's promote our Organic Farming in schools.

Chair: Okay, Councilor Junjun, Councilor Junjun is mentioned in Article 2, line 185, number 9, okay? Councilor Karlos Buted is recognized.

SP Member K. E. Buted: Thank you very much, Madam Chair, good morning to everyone. I apologize for not being able to share properly as I am not a farmer. Madam Chair, I just want to express that I'm in support of organic farmers, although I do not know the specifics of farming, but in general, we are aware of the importance of organic farming. Madam Chair, I will be technical here, in Sec. 5, Batangas City Technical Committee on Organic Agriculture, perhaps we could switch items A and B, starting with the composition followed by the function because if a reader wonders who the committee is and how it was formed, they see the functions first, which might be confusing. It should be rearranged, and it is written there in the composition. Composition, the council, so let's add to the council, the technical committee shall be composed of the following. Because it is written in Section 5, Batangas City Technical Committee, there might be a misinterpretation that the technical committee and the council mentioned are different, that's it. And Madam Chair, regarding the functions provision, no.7, it is written here, the committee shall have the following functions, so we know the difference between shall and may, shall is stronger and since this is an ordinance it needs to be absolute and not negotiable. No.7, develop incentive mechanisms, in the functions, when we say incentive mechanisms, it includes items such as subsidies, crop insurance, and support systems. So, it might also be important for our OCVAS to ensure that before we allocate a budget, as mentioned earlier by Mr. M, we have line budgeting to observe the planning implementation. This will allow us to determine what kind of support systems, types of subsidies, and crop insurance are included in the ordinance. However, when it comes to implementation, we must be certain of what is stated here.

Chair: Thank you, Councilor Buted, everything you said is noted, sorry for the suddenness, it's noted. Any questions, any further comments, ma'am Flora?

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: The incentives were also mentioned, and perhaps on our side, we might struggle, yes, if there is no subsidy, the subsidies for the certification fees. Because the payment to certify a certain product as organic is substantial, farmers will not be able to afford it, as well as the subsidies for certification fees. When it comes to obtaining certification for their product, it is not us who will pay for the certification of the product.

SP Member N. Dimacuha: If I may, madam chair, which is what I told you earlier, Section 336 states that the budget is only for that purpose. Our purpose is for organic farming which includes the issuance of the certificate, it's all part of the same program, where will it come from?

Mrs. Flora Alvarez: The city government will pay.

SP Member N. Dimacuha: Yes, who will issue this certificate, is it from the Department of Agriculture? Mrs. Flora Alvarez: It comes from the national board, as there are certifying bodies.

SP Member L. Gamboa, Jr.: So, you will endorse the product to the national level, and then they will determine if it's organic, they will issue the certificate and also collect the payment, how much do you think that would be?

Chair: Mr. Perlada.

Mr. Manolo Perlada: The intention of the program is good, it's important to appreciate organic products. In my opinion, it seems the IDC is not included in the ordinance for

people to appreciate the importance of organic produce. The problem will be with the buyers; the product is there, it may not be certified but we believe some things are organic because they are obtained organically. However, as long as consumers do not appreciate the value of organic produce, our products will not progress because we still prefer to buy even if the Melon has a slight blemish, although it's not deep, it's just on the surface, but we still won't buy it, we will still choose the perfectly smooth melon. The same goes for bananas, eggplants, okra. What's important is, for example, if the okra is much curved, it might be organic but no one will buy such curved okra. So, perhaps we need to include in our ordinance the establishment of an IDC, or how consumers can appreciate the importance of organic produce. The Nutrition Office... and other government functionaries need to be involved because what happens is they just keep producing products with no buyers, leading to spoilage. Sometimes, as the ladies say, it will just be fed to the pigs, and then, the pigs become organic too.

Chair: Thank you, Mr. Perlada. That will be the last from Councilor Karlos Buted.

SP Member K. E. Buted: Thank you very much, Madam Chair, I apologize for not being very open to discussion. Regarding the Funding and Final Provisions, it was mentioned earlier that there seems to be a fund of 1 million, but Madam Chair, my personal suggestion is to make adjustments in Article 5, Section 26, on funding requirements to be more flexible. I know that it will be supported by our city government. The funding requirement states that the City Government of Batangas shall appropriate an annual allocation of such amount as may be deemed necessary and requisite. That's it. Because if we say shall be appropriate 1 million for the initial amount but stick to the 1 million and then decide to just add more, what if it turns out that we need 1.5 million or 2 million? So, the 1 million seems quite small for the program, really small, because if we think about it, the ordinance is written to shall and 1 million for the initial, what if our assessment shows that we need more, so it would be better to... thank you.

Chair: Good, thank you Councilor Karlos, now Mr. Victor Malibiran.

Mr. Victor Malibiran: I just want to share that if possible, we should have a designated market for our organic produce because here's the thing, if we mix our organic produce with the non-organic ones, of course, it's somewhat, let's say, really disadvantageous for our organic produce. Sir Manolo is right in saying that our consumers are fond of beautiful things, so it is only right that we have a designated market for our organic produce, thank you, madam chair.

Chair: Okay, any questions from our fellow councillors? If there are none, this committee hearing is adjourned.

HEARING ADJOURNMENT: 11:17 AM

X-----X

CERTIFICATION

I hereby certify that the foregoing transcript is true and correct according to my understanding, knowledge and belief.

ADMIN. ASST. V

C E R T I F I C A T I O N

This is to certify that this copy is the official transcript of record of Committee Hearing, held on November 24, 2023 at Sangguniang Panlungsod Session Hall.

SENIOR ADMIN. ASST.